

A STUDY OF THE GRAVITATIONAL LENS
0957+561

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Abstract

The gravitationally lensed source 0957+561 A,B is the subject of the observations and lens modelling described in this thesis. New optical and radio observations are presented which are used to investigate a number of different lens mass distributions, including a 'double lens' system in which the lenses are located at different redshifts. These studies have been carried out with the underlying aim of determining the mass distribution of the main lensing galaxy G1.

Radio observations made with the European VLBI Network (EVN) have resulted in the production of the first VLBI hybrid maps of the A and B images. These confirm to high precision previous observations of core-jet structure and support the view that the images have opposite parities.

A wide field hybrid map centred on the B image shows the weak compact component G', which is generally believed to be the core of the main lensing galaxy G1. A comparison has been made between the position of G' in the EVN map and the position of the associated component G in a recent MERLIN map. This strongly suggests that the radio emission from the lensing galaxy is composed of a flat spectrum compact component (G') and steep spectrum extended emission lying ≥ 78 mas to the north west. An alternative explanation is that G' is the third image and the extended emission is associated with the lensing galaxy G1. However, this implies an error in the optical position of G1.

The technique of multi-slit spectroscopy has been used to obtain optical spectra of the brightest objects in the field surrounding 0957+561 A,B. Redshift measurements have been used to separate galaxies which are members of the lensing cluster at $z \approx 0.355$ from field galaxies. This has allowed a luminosity weighted centre to be determined for the cluster. It lies close to the main lensing galaxy G1, about 20 arcseconds further east than previously suggested. Cross-correlation of the galaxy spectra implies a cluster line of sight velocity dispersion ~ 548 km s⁻¹. A surprising result

is the discovery of four galaxies lying close to each other on the sky with the same redshift, $z \approx 0.503$. It is not clear whether this is just an isolated group of galaxies or the brightest members of a rich cluster.

Several lens models including both double and single plane systems have been constructed. In all successful models the faint third image is predicted to lie ≈ 110 mas south of the main lensing galaxy, G1. If the four galaxies at $z \approx 0.503$ can be classified as a small group then their effect on the imaging process will be minimal. If, however, these galaxies are members of a cluster similar in size and extent to that found at $z \approx 0.355$, they may have an important role to play. Three independent solutions (one of which is a double plane model) all suggest that $\sim 10^{12} M_{\odot}$ is a reasonable estimate of the mass of G1 out to the A image. Most of the mass in the cluster must be in the form of dark matter with $M/L \sim 340$.

Preface

Previous study

The author graduated from the University of Glasgow in July 1986 and in October of that year registered for the the M.Sc. course in Radio Astronomy at the Nuffield Radio Astronomy Laboratories, Department of Physics, University of Manchester. He was awarded the Diploma of Advanced Studies in Science in September 1987. The author registered for the degree of Ph.D. at the same institution in October 1987.

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Declaration

The author had no part in the original conception of the work presented in this thesis, nor was he responsible for the software used to gather or reduce the radio or optical observations. Unless otherwise stated the author has been solely responsible for the data reduction and analysis of these data. In addition, the software used to obtain the lens models presented in chapter 6 was written entirely by the author.

No portion of the work referred to in this thesis has been submitted in support of an application for another degree or qualification at this or any other university or institute of learning.

Michael A. Garrett,
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Macclesfield,
Cheshire.

May 1990.

*To my
Father and Grandfather*

“Of a’ the airts the wind can blaw
I dearly like the west,
For there the bonnie lassie lives,
The lassie I lo’e best”

by *Robert Burns* – taken from *Of a’ the airts*.

‘He fair could play, the piper, he tore at your heart marching there with the tune leaping up the moor and echoing across the loch, folk said that Chris Tavendale alone shed never a tear, she stood quiet, holding her boy by the hand, looking down on Blawearie’s fields till the playing was over. And syne folk saw that the dark had come and began to stream down the hill, leaving her there, some were uncertain and looked them back. But they saw the minister was standing behind her, waiting for her, they’d the last of the light with them up there, and maybe they didn’t need it or heed it, you can do without the day if you’ve a lamp quiet-lighted and kind in your heart.’

by *Lewis Grassie Gibbon* – A Scots Quair, Sunset Song.

“Much is forgiven to those who succeed”

by *Otto von Bismarck*.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

There is no great chance of observing the phenomenon.

— Einstein (1936)

1.1 Historical background

In 1916, Einstein announced his general theory of relativity. Unlike his previous special theory, the general theory introduced the concept that space-time could be curved and distorted by the presence of matter or energy. One of the chief predictions of this theory (Einstein 1916) is that light rays, passing a distance $\bar{r}$ from an object of mass M , would be deflected through an angle $\bar{\alpha}$. For a point mass, $\bar{\alpha}$ is given by

$$\bar{\alpha}(\bar{r}) = \frac{4GM\bar{r}}{c^2|\bar{r}|^2} \quad (1.1)$$

where G is the constant of gravitation and c is the speed of light.

Sir Arthur Eddington observed this effect during the 1919 solar eclipse: observing stars close to the Sun's edge, he measured a displacement from their apparent positions. The results were scattered around one half and twice the value predicted by equation 1.1. However this was to be expected; the experiments of Eddington and his co-workers had only 30% accuracy. It is only recently, with the advent of Very Long Baseline radio Interferometry (VLBI), that observers have been able to confirm Einstein's original prediction to high accuracy, e.g. (Robertson & Carter 1984).

According to Barnothy (1989) the possibility that a massive object might act as a gravitational lens, producing multiple images of a distant source seems to have occurred to both Lodge and Eddington and (Lodge 1919, Eddington 1923). Indeed it was reported by Zwicky that in 1923, E. B. Frost (director of Yerkes Observatory) proposed that a survey should be carried out to look for just this effect, however the program seems never to have got started. The first recorded suggestion that a massive object might act as a gravitational lens was made by Chwolson (1924). He showed that if a star was observed close to the line of sight of a more distant star, then two images of

the more distant star might be formed, but he did not make any calculations. By coincidence Chwolson's letter appeared just above an unrelated item by Einstein. However, it was not until twelve years later, (and apparently in ignorance of Chwolson's original result) that Einstein took up the problem.

Acting on a suggestion by an obscure Czech electrical engineer (R.W. Mandl), Einstein (1936) published a short calculation showing that if two stars at different distances were exactly coincident in the sky, the image of the more distant one would form a ring. Einstein noted that for very close alignments the observer could expect to see the background star highly amplified with respect to the original undeflected source. He concluded however, that the ring (now referred to as the Einstein ring) would be too small to be resolved telescopically and that in any case, such a chance alignment was very unlikely. Nevertheless, Zwicky (1937a,b) in two letters pointed out that lensing events involving distant extragalactic objects such as galaxies and clusters were 'practically a certainty'. He also realised that such lensing events could provide a very direct method for determining the mass of the lensing galaxies.

The subject fell into obscurity until the early 1960's when Klimov (1963) in the Soviet Union, Liebes (1964) in the USA and Refsdal(1964a) in Norway each published detailed calculations of the characteristics expected of lensed images. With the discovery of quasars a number of people began to show an increasing interest in lensing e.g. Barnothy (1965), Sanitt (1971), Press & Gunn (1973), and Gott & Gunn (1974). In particular, Bourassa & Kantowski (1975) further improved the theoretical side by introducing more realistic distributed and transparent lens models to their calculations. These theoretical papers were to lay the foundations of gravitational optics. However, further progress could not be made until the subject of lensing moved from the realm of being a theoretical possibility to an observational reality.

1.2 The discovery of the 'double quasar' 0957+561 A,B

The double quasar 0957 + 561 A,B first came to light as a member of the Jodrell Bank 966 MHz survey (for a complete review see Walsh 1989). It was first detected on the 4th of January 1973 during one of the survey's many raster scans. Using the Palomar sky survey, Porcas *et al.* (1980) identified the radio source with two very blue stellar-like objects with similar magnitudes, separated by only 6 arcseconds and aligned roughly North - South on the sky.

Following up the optical identifications, Walsh, Carswell & Weymann (1979) made spectroscopic observations of both objects. The results were surprising: both were identified as QSO's with very similar spectra and identical (within the measurement errors) emission and absorption line redshifts ($z_{em} = 1.4105$ and $z_{obs} = 1.390$). This startling discovery led Walsh, Carswell and Weymann to suggest that they were seeing two images of a single quasar formed by an intervening massive object (see Figure 1.1). Subsequent observations ranging from radio frequencies to the ultraviolet have consistently confirmed that their original hypothesis is correct.

Figure 1.1: A schematic representation of how the gravitational field of a galaxy can form three images of a quasar on the plane of the sky. Note that the sizes of the angles of deflection are greatly exaggerated.

1.3 Further observational and theoretical Progress

The discovery of 0957 + 561 A,B resulted in rapid development in the field both observationally and theoretically. Here we briefly review the progress which has been made over the past decade.

1.3.1 Observational developments

There are now at least eight other lensed quasar candidates for which extensive observations have been made. Of those eight, four must be considered strong cases - 1115+030 (Weymann *et al.* 1980), 2016+112 (Lawrence *et al.* 1984), 2237+031 (Huchra *et al.* 1985) 1413+171 (Magain *et al.* 1988), two still remain somewhat controversial

1635+267 (Djorgovski & Spinrad 1984) and 2345+007 (Weedman *et al.* 1982), and two are probably not lenses 0023+171 (Hewitt *et al.* 1987) and 1146+111 (Turner *et al.* 1986).

In addition, ongoing optical and radio surveys for lensed quasars e.g. Crampton *et al.* (1989), Webster, Hewitt & Irwin (1988) and Hewitt *et al.* (1989) have produced several promising (although preliminary) candidates including 1429-008 (Hewitt *et al.* 1989), 1042+178, 2018+102, 2113+100 (Hewitt 1986) and 1120+019 (Djorgovski & Meylan 1989).

Lensing has also been suggested for sources other than quasars. Hammer, Nottale & Le Fèvre (1986) have proposed that some radio galaxies (e.g. 3C 324, 3C 368) may be lensed by foreground galaxies lying close to or on the line of sight. This they believe can explain the over-luminosity of these sources and the complex morphology they exhibit under sub-arcsecond spatial resolution.

The discovery by Lynds & Petrosian (1986) of a giant luminous arc in the cluster Abell 370 (Figure 1.2) is perhaps the most dramatic manifestation of gravitational lensing yet observed. At least four arcs have been observed in other clusters: 2244-02 (Lynds & Petrosian 1986), A2218 (Pello-Descayre *et al.* 1988), A963 (Lavery & Henry 1988) and 0500-24 (Giraud 1988). In addition, Fort *et al.* (1988) have reported that deep CCD frames of A370 reveal six smaller arcs. The arcs have been interpreted by Soucail *et al.* (1987) as distorted images of background galaxies lensed by the foreground cluster. Soucail *et al.* (1988) have obtained spectra of the largest arc ($z_{arc} = 0.724$, $z_{cl} = 0.374$) which supports their hypothesis.

Two remarkable ring-shaped radio sources 1131+0456 (Hewitt *et al.* 1988) and 0414+0534 (Hewitt *et al.* 1989) are the most recent lens candidates to emerge from the VLA gravitational lens survey. Hewitt *et al.* (1988) believe that 1131+0456 may be the lensed image of a typical radio galaxy that consists of a core and two lobes. One of the lobes falls directly behind the lens mass and is distorted into a nearly complete Einstein ring.

The importance of micro-lensing (lensing by individual stars which are close to or within the light path) has been highlighted with the detection by Irwin *et al.* (1989) of an uncorrelated change in the brightness of one of the four images observed in 2237+0305. Stickel, Fried & Kühr (1989) have produced further evidence that micro-lensing may be responsible for the variability of the Bl Lac object 0846+51 W1.

Figure 1.2: The giant arc in Abell 370. Note also the faint double arc systems referenced as (A1,A2) and (A3,A4); and two other elongated structures A5 and A6 (after Fort *et al.* 1988).

1.3.2 Theoretical progress

On the theoretical side much of the work in the last ten years has concentrated on the statistics of lensing, the effects of micro-lensing and modelling of specific lens systems.

Turner, Ostriker & Gott (1984) were able to show that the most probable image separations should be around 0.5 to 1 arcsecond. They noted that instrumental selection effects were probably responsible for the lack of such close spaced systems.

Chang and Refsdal 1979, 1984; and Young (1981) showed that the amplification factor of lensed images could be strongly affected by individual stars lying close to the light path.

Young, Gunn, Kristian, Oke & Westphal (1981, hereafter YGKOW), Higgs (1984), Narasimha, Subramanian & Chitre (1984) and Greenfield, Roberts & Burke (1985) were able to model 0957 + 561 A,B to varying degrees of success. All four groups

agreed that large amounts of dark matter were necessary to satisfy the observational constraints.

The application of Fermat's principle by Schneider (1985) and Blandford & Narayan (1986) resulted in a new formalism for treating gravitational lensing which improved the visualisation of image formation. New and simple numerical imaging procedures were devised by Schramm & Kayser (1987) which can calculate the image positions, shapes and brightnesses for any lens model without inverting the lens equation. The discovery of extended sources being lensed prompted Kayser & Schramm (1988) to develop a method of reconstructing the source given an image (Digital Source Reconstruction - DiSoR), and this has been applied successfully by Kochanek *et al.* (1989) to VLA maps of the Einstein ring radio source 1131+0456.

1.4 Why are lensed systems important ?

Long before the discovery of the first gravitational lens system, Zwicky (1937a,b) and Refsdal (1964b,1966) had recognised their potential to determine the mass of galaxies and clusters by a method which was independent of traditional dynamical means. This is easily understood, since the angular separation of a multiply imaged source is proportional to the square root of the mass of the deflector (lens). Moreover, since the light deflection depends only on the gravitational potential of the lens, it is sensitive to all forms of matter: luminous or dark. Hence, the study of lensed systems both individually and collectively can provide clues to the nature of dark matter.

The way in which light is propagated between the source and observer along two or more neighbouring ray paths means that the images we see depend on gross properties of the universe, such as Hubble's constant, H_0 . Given a complete knowledge of an observed case, including the time delay between variations in the different images, it may be possible to determine the distance to the source and hence H_0 itself Refsdal (1966). It seems unlikely that such knowledge will ever be available for any individual lens system, and as a result, only upper limits for H_0 will be obtained. The combined results obtained from an ensemble of lenses may be more useful.

Image brightness variations due to micro-lensing can be used (Canizares 1981) to infer the size and structure of the compact source (e.g. quasars). The magnitude and time scale of the variations can also be used to place limits on the mass of the micro-lens itself.

It is now widely appreciated that gravitational lens systems can offer many interesting astrophysical applications. Perhaps surprisingly the first lens system to be discovered 0957 + 561 A,B still has an important role to play in this field. Although many other lensed systems have been discovered 0957 + 561 A,B is still the best studied and most secure lens system. It is unique amongst other candidates for the following three reasons:

- it is a radio source on arcsecond and milliarcsecond scales. VLBI core-jet structure is observed in both images (Porcas *et al.* 1981), and has placed strong constraints on lens models.
- comparison of the A and B VLBI jet fluxes have allowed an accurate determination of the amplification ratio between the images, which is not affected by micro-lensing
- the lens has been unambiguously identified by Stockton (1980) and Young *et al.* 1980, YGKOW; with a cluster of galaxies the brightest of which is a giant elliptical ($z \approx 0.36$) that lies only $1''$ from the B image.

1.5 Overview of this thesis

The double quasar, 0957+561 A,B is the subject of the observations and lens modelling described in this thesis. The underlying aim of this study is to investigate the mass distribution of the main lensing galaxy 'G1'.

To that end observations have been made which provide new modelling constraints. In Chapter 4 we present the first VLBI hybrid maps of the A and B images. Optical spectra of the brightest galaxies in the field have also been obtained and the results are presented in Chapter 5. Previous observations of the double quasar are discussed in Chapter 3.

In Chapter 6 a description is given of two major modelling programs that have been written during the course of this project. One of these has been used to examine lens models proposed by other authors and the findings of this exercise are discussed. We also present new lens models including those involving a double lens system (lenses located at different redshifts) which are consistent with the optical and radio observations of the previous three chapters. Particular attention is focussed on the effect different lens models have on the derived mass distribution of 'G1'.

Chapter 7 is the concluding chapter and summarises the results presented in this thesis and makes some recommendations for future work.

Since any discussion of the results with regard to the gravitational lens effect requires an understanding of the imaging process, we begin (Chapter 2) with a brief introduction to the theory of gravitational lensing.

Chapter 2

Gravitational Lens Theory

Gravitational lenses provide a theorist's heaven and an observer's hell. —
P.J.E. Peebles.

2.1 Introduction

The detailed theory of gravitational lensing has been treated by many authors (see Bourassa & Kantowski 1975, YGKOW and Blandford & Narayan 1986 for details). Only a brief outline of the more relevant aspects of this theory are presented here.

We begin by deriving the lens equation for a single lens plane and extend this to the 'double lens' case. The vector formalism introduced by Young *et al.* (1980) is used throughout. The deflection of light by a transparent mass is also treated and a formula for the bend angle derived. Extensive use is made of bend angle diagrams to highlight established theoretical results. Finally, we discuss the effects of micro-lensing in lensed systems.

2.2 The lens equation

A typical gravitationally lensed system consists of a deflector (A) situated at a redshift z_A , that deflects light from a distant source (S) situated at a redshift z_S , $z_S > z_A$. This deflection results in the production of at least one image of the source, seen by an observer at (O). Figure 2.1 illustrates the observer-lens-source geometry. In Figure 2.1 D_{OA} , D_{OS} and D_{AS} represent the observer-lens, observer-source and lens-source angular-diameter distances. If angular-diameter distances are used, angular sizes and their associated perpendicular proper distances obey the principles of Euclidean geometry. Following Young *et al.* (1980), Narasimha, Subramanian & Chitre (1984), Higgs (1984) and Greenfield, Roberts & Burke (1985) we adopt a standard Friedmann-Robertson-Walker cosmological model with $\Lambda = 0$, $q_0 = 0$ and $H_0 = 60$ km s⁻¹ Mpc⁻¹.

For a Friedmann universe, Gunn (1966) gives the angular-diameter distance D_{ij} between points i and j at redshifts z_i and z_j ($z_i < z_j$) as

Figure 2.1: Geometry of a gravitational lens system.

$$D_{ij} = \frac{c(x_j^2 - x_i^2)}{2H_0(x_j^2 x_i)} \quad (2.1)$$

where $x_i = 1 + z_i$ and $x_j = 1 + z_j$.

If point i is the observer, this reduces to the familiar form

$$D_{oj} = \frac{c(x_j^2 - 1)}{2H_0 x_j^2} \quad (2.2)$$

To derive the lens equation we introduce the following assumptions:

- the deflection is sudden i.e. it occurs at the deflector plane only. This is a good approximation if the deflector size is $\ll$ than the lens-source, observer-lens distances.
- the deflection angle is small, so that bending formulas in weak gravitational fields may be used.
- the deflector is transparent and its surface mass density is a smooth function of impact parameter i.e. the effects of micro-lensing may be ignored.

Let us now return to Figure 2.1. We begin by tracing the path of a light ray which starts at the source (S), and is deflected by the lens at A, before reaching the observer

at O. If the gravitational field is weak, the deflection $\bar{\alpha}$ (sometimes referred to as the vector bend angle) will be small, depending only on the distribution of the surface mass density of the deflector as projected onto a plane perpendicular to the line of sight and coincident with the centre of the deflector. This plane is known as the *lens plane* or the *image plane*. We denote the two dimensional angular position (x, y) of the undeflected source in the lens plane by $\bar{\theta}_S$, the angular position of the image by $\bar{\theta}_I$ and the bend angle by $\bar{\alpha}(\bar{\theta}_I)$. We adopt the usual astronomical convention of describing angular displacements along east-west and north-south axes by x and y .

The lens equation for a single lens follows from the simple geometry of Figure 2.1,

$$\bar{\theta}_I D_{OS} = \bar{\theta}_S D_{OS} + \bar{\alpha}(\bar{\theta}_I) D_{AS} \quad (2.3)$$

or rearranging,

$$\bar{\theta}_I = \bar{\theta}_S + \bar{\alpha}(\bar{\theta}_I) \frac{D_{AS}}{D_{OS}} \quad (2.4)$$

The lens equation describes a surjective mapping i.e. different image points are mapped onto the same source point but different source points can never map onto the same image point. Except for very simple cases, solving for image positions, given the source position and the bend angle at $\bar{\theta}_I$, is non trivial. We will discuss the various numerical methods which have been employed in a later chapter. Note that if more than one deflector is present the total deflection is just the vector sum of the deflections associated with each lens i.e. equation 2.4 becomes

$$\bar{\theta}_I = \bar{\theta}_S + \sum_{k=1}^n \bar{\alpha}_k(\bar{\theta}_I) \frac{D_{AS}}{D_{OS}} \quad (2.5)$$

2.2.1 The lens equation with two lens planes

We extend the previous formalism to the case in which the lens consists of two mass distributions which are at located at different redshifts from the observer. This so called 'double lens' situation has been considered by Blandford & Narayan (1986) and Kochanek & Apostolakis (1988). Figure 2.2 shows a possible double lens configuration. As before the D_{ij} are angular-diameter distances and assumptions detailed for the single lens case still apply.

Simple geometry requires that

$$\bar{\theta}_I = \bar{\theta}_S + \bar{\alpha}_A(\bar{\theta}_I) \frac{D_{AS}}{D_{OS}} + \bar{\alpha}_B(\bar{\chi}) \frac{D_{BS}}{D_{OS}} \quad (2.6)$$

Figure 2.2: Geometry of a double lens system

where $\bar{\alpha}_A$ and $\bar{\alpha}_B$ are the bend angles produced by the lenses at A and B respectively, and $\bar{\chi}$ is the vector angle which specifies the point at which the ray intercepts the second lens plane. The vector angle, $\bar{\chi}$, is given by

$$\bar{\chi} = \bar{\theta}_I - \bar{\alpha}_A \frac{D_{AB}}{D_{OB}} \quad (2.7)$$

It is reassuring to note that if the lens at B is moved towards the lens plane defined by A then equation 2.6 reduces to the single-plane equation 2.5 i.e. $D_{AB} \rightarrow 0$, $D_{OB} \rightarrow D_{OA}$ and $\bar{\chi} \rightarrow \bar{\theta}_I$.

2.3 Light deflection by a transparent lens

In this section we outline the methods involved in deriving the bend angle α for a transparent, elliptically symmetric lens. This problem was originally treated by Bourassa & Kantowski (1975).

The general theory of relativity (Einstein 1916) predicts that the deflection ($\bar{\alpha}$) experienced by a ray of light passing close to a point mass is equal to

$$\bar{\alpha}(\bar{r}) = \frac{4GM\bar{r}}{c^2|\bar{r}|^2} \quad (2.8)$$

where G is the gravitational constant, c is the speed of light, M is the mass of the point mass centred at the origin of the deflector plane and $\vec{r}$ is the vector from the point mass to the incident light ray.

With the exception of black holes, stars and other compact objects, masses (such as galaxies and clusters of galaxies) cannot be treated as point masses. Instead these must be treated as transparent, distributed masses. Bourassa, Kantowski & Norton (1973) derived a bend angle formula (analogous to equation 2.3) for a distributed mass by dividing the extended source into a number of point sources and adding the bend angles due to each of these point sources. If $\vec{r}_i$ are the vector positions of the i masses and $\vec{r}_0$ is the impact position of the incident light ray in the deflector plane then $\vec{\alpha}$ can be written,

$$\vec{\alpha}(\vec{r}) = \sum_i \frac{4GM_i(\vec{r}_0 - \vec{r}_i)}{c^2|\vec{r}_0 - \vec{r}_i|^2} \quad (2.9)$$

Introducing the surface mass density, Σ , of the deflector (as projected on to the deflector plane),

$$\Sigma(\vec{r}) \equiv \Sigma(x, y) \quad (2.10)$$

equation 2.9 can be generalised further to give

$$\vec{\alpha}(\vec{r}) = \frac{4G}{c^2} \int \frac{\Sigma(x, y)(x_0 - x, y_0 - y)}{(x_0 - x)^2 + (y_0 - y)^2} dx dy \quad (2.11)$$

for a ray of light passing normally through the (x, y) deflector plane at position (x_0, y_0) .

Following Bourassa & Kantowski (1975) we simplify things still further, by confining ourselves to elliptically symmetric surface mass distributions whose axis of symmetry lies in the plane of the sky. In this case the surface density is a function of the major axis b and the axial ratio of the ellipse $\cos \beta$. From Figure 2.3 it is apparent that

$$(x, y) = (b \cos \psi, b \cos \beta \sin \psi) \quad (2.12)$$

and that

$$dx dy = b \cos \beta d\psi db \quad (2.13)$$

Figure 2.3: The co-ordinates associated with the elliptically symmetric surface mass distribution

Using these relations we can rewrite equation 2.11 as

$$\bar{\alpha}(x, y) = \frac{4G \cos \beta}{c^2} \int_0^\infty \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{\Sigma(b) (\bar{r}_0 - \bar{r}(b, \psi)) b}{|\bar{r}_0 - \bar{r}(b, \psi)|^2} d\psi db \quad (2.14)$$

The determination of the integral in equation 2.14 is simplified by replacing the vectors with complex numbers i.e. we write $z_0 = x_0 + iy_0$ and $z = x + iy$. Noting that

$$z = b(\cos \psi + i \cos \beta \sin \psi) \quad (2.15)$$

the complex conjugate of α is then

$$\alpha^*(z_0) = \frac{4G \cos \beta}{c^2} \int_0^\infty \Sigma(b) \left(\int_0^{2\pi} \frac{d\psi}{z_0 - z(b, \psi)} \right) b db \quad (2.16)$$

Following Higgs (1984) the inner integral of equation 2.16 may be written,

$$\int_0^{2\pi} \frac{d\psi}{z_0 - z(b, \psi)} = \frac{\pm 2\pi}{(z_0^2 - b^2 \sin^2 \beta)^{1/2}} \quad (2.17)$$

The bend angle can then be written as a one-dimensional integral of $\Sigma(b)$, rather

than a two dimensional integral. This considerably simplifies the numerical integration required to calculate $\bar{\alpha}$. Hence the complex conjugate of the bend angle, α^* , for a ray of light which intercepts the deflector at

$$z_0 = b_0(\cos \psi_0 + i \sin \psi_0 \cos \beta) \quad (2.18)$$

is just given by

$$\alpha^*(z_0) = \frac{\pm 8\pi G \cos \beta}{c^2} \int_0^{b_0} \frac{\Sigma(b) b db}{(z_0^2 - b^2 \sin^2 \beta)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad (2.19)$$

2.3.1 The lens mass distribution

In order to calculate a value for $\bar{\alpha}$ for any particular combination of b , $\cos \beta$ and z_0 a model for the lens mass distribution must be assumed. Figure 2.4 shows the bend angle $\bar{\alpha}$ as a function of impact parameter b for a point mass and a King model mass distribution. According to Bahcall (1977) the surface density $\Sigma(r)$ of a galaxy or cluster of galaxies can be quite accurately described by a King model distribution (King 1966).

Figure 2.4: The bend angle function for two common mass distributions: a point mass and a King model.

A King model for a galaxy can be completely specified by three parameters:

- the dimensionless cut off energy (W_0)
- the central density of the galaxy (ρ_0)
- and the core radius (τ_c) of the galaxy (defined by $\rho(\tau_c) = \rho_0/2$)

It is probably prudent to air a note of caution at this point. The density profiles of galaxies with which models are compared can only be reliably determined down to about $0.01\Sigma_0$. Hence, we only have a very limited knowledge of the surface density distribution in the outer parts of galaxies and clusters of galaxies. This is an important point to remember as it is in the outer parts that most lensing events take place. The King model can only be considered an approximation to the mass distributions of real galaxies and clusters of galaxies.

YGKOW introduced a dimensionless form for equation 2.19 by defining the structural length, a , of the galaxy to be one third of the the core radius, r_c and then defining the velocity dispersion σ_v by

$$\sigma_v^2 = 4\pi G\rho_0 a^2 \quad (2.20)$$

where ρ_0 is the central density. Following YGKOW we obtain the dimensionless quantities:

$$b_* = b/a, z_* = z/a, \Sigma_*(b_*) = \Sigma(b)/\rho_0 a$$

Observations of the velocity dispersion of a nearby cD galaxy by Dressler (1979) prompted Young *et al.* (1980) to assume a cut-off energy of $W_0 = 12$. YGKOW also produced an interpolation formula which could approximate the King model surface mass distribution:

$$\Sigma_*(b_*) = C_1(1 + (C_2 b_*)^2)^{-1/2} + C_3(1 + (C_4 b_*)^2)^{-1/2} \quad (2.21)$$

where $C_1 = 10.249$, $C_2 = 0.385$, $C_3 = -4.250$ and $C_4 = 0.193$.

King models ($W_0 = 12$) and YGKOW's interpolation formula have been used in the lens models described elsewhere in this thesis.

In its dimensionless form equation 2.19 becomes

$$\bar{\alpha}^-(z_*) = \pm 2 \frac{\sigma_v^2}{c^2} \cos \beta \int_0^{b_*} \frac{b'_* \Sigma_*(b'_*) db'_*}{(z_*^2 - b'^2_* \sin^2 \beta)^{1/2}} \quad (2.22)$$

The mass of the lens within impact parameter b_* may be written:

$$M(b_*) = \frac{\sigma_v^2 a \cos \beta}{2G} \int_0^{b_*} \Sigma(b) b db \quad (2.23)$$

If $\Sigma(b)$ is replaced by YGKOW interpolation formula then the integral in equation 2.23 can easily be determined. One important result from relation 2.23 is that only the mass within the contour of the projected mass distribution that passes through the image located furthest from the centre of the lens influences the imaging. The total mass within this contour is more usually quoted in lens studies, since the total mass is generally very model dependent.

2.4 Important aspects of lens theory

In this section we briefly discuss some of the more important aspects of gravitational lens theory. The treatment presented here is not intended to be rigorous. We make use of bend angle diagrams to derive many of the following results.

2.4.1 Probability estimates for gravitational lensing

A natural scale length which is used frequently in gravitational lens studies is the Einstein radius, a_{ER} . This is the radius of the ring that would appear (in the plane of the lens) if the lensing object (considered to be a point mass) and source were perfectly aligned:

$$a_{ER} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{4GM}{c^2}\right) \left(\frac{D_{OS}D_{AS}}{D_{OA}}\right)} \quad (2.24)$$

For typical cosmological distances this can be re-written as

$$a_{ER} = 0.01 \sqrt{\frac{M}{M_{\odot}}} \text{(parsecs)} \quad (2.25)$$

or on an angular scale,

$$\theta_{ER} = 10^{-6} \sqrt{\frac{M}{M_{\odot}}} \text{(arcseconds)} \quad (2.26)$$

The Einstein radius can be thought of as a cross section for gravitational lensing. For a randomly located sources the probability of significant lensing effects occurring is given by

$$P = \frac{\pi \theta_{ER}^2}{4\pi} = \frac{GM}{c^2} \frac{D_{AS}}{D_{OS} D_{OA}} = \frac{D_{AS}}{D_{OS}} \left(\frac{\phi}{c^2} \right) \quad (2.27)$$

where ϕ is the gravitational potential of the lens at the observer. If we consider more than one deflector then the optical depth, τ , for lensing is just

$$\tau \approx \frac{\phi_T}{c^2} \quad (2.28)$$

where ϕ_T is now the total gravitational potential from all possible deflectors. For our own galaxy $\phi_T/c^2 \approx 10^{-6}$ so that as Einstein (1936) concluded lensing between stars in our own galaxy is highly unlikely. We can also see from equation 2.26 that even if such an event were to occur the image splitting for a solar mass star is extremely small $\approx 10^{-6}$ arcseconds. This is far beyond the reach of current or anticipated instrumental resolutions.

For more distant sources at cosmological distances the probability can be estimated by following the argument of Press & Gunn (1973). If n is the deflector number density and D is some typical cosmological distance then

$$\tau = n a_{ER}^2 D \approx \frac{GM}{c^2} n D^2 \approx \epsilon \Omega \quad (2.29)$$

where Ω is the density parameter and ϵ is the fraction of all mass found in lenses. If the deflectors considered are galaxies then $\epsilon \Omega \approx 0.01$. We observe as did Zwicky (1937a,b) that there is a relatively high probability of observing gravitational lensing between distant extragalactic objects.

2.4.2 Bend angle diagrams

Let us consider a spherically symmetric lens in which case the determination of the bend angle reduces to a one-dimensional problem. From equation 2.4 it is obvious that images are found at angles which are solutions of

$$\bar{\alpha}(\bar{\theta}_I) = \frac{D_{OS}}{D_{AS}} (\bar{\theta}_I - \bar{\theta}_S) \quad (2.30)$$

Note that the l.h.s. of equation 2.30 depends only on the structure of the lens while the r.h.s. depends only on the geometry of the lens system. A physically reasonable

Figure 2.6: A graphical solution to the lens equation for a typical distributed lens mass distribution.

this chapter. Nevertheless it is clear that, singular cases aside, the number of images is always odd.

2.4.4 Conditions required for multiple imaging

We can also use the bend angle diagram of Figure 2.6 to estimate the conditions that are necessary for multiple imaging. We note that for multiple imaging to occur,

$$\alpha \frac{D_{AS}}{D_{OS}} \geq \theta_C \approx 2\tau_C D_{OA} \quad (2.31)$$

or rearranging

$$\tau_C < \frac{\alpha D_{OA} D_{AS}}{2 D_{OS}} \quad (2.32)$$

for cosmological distances $D_{OA} D_{AS} / D_{OS}$ is of order 700 Mpc which implies,

$$\tau_C < 1.7\alpha'' \text{ (kpc)}$$

form for α is drawn in Figure 2.5. When the r.h.s. of equation 2.30 is also plotted on the same Figure with a common set of axes this is known as a *bend angle diagram*. The intersections of the curve $\alpha(\theta)$ with the line $L(\theta) = \frac{D_{OS}}{D_{AS}}(\bar{\theta}_I - \bar{\theta}_S)$ will determine the positions of the image. Note that the slope of $L(\theta)$ is D_{OS}/D_{AS} and the intercept on the x-axis is just θ_S . As it is possible more than one image will be formed it is necessary to extend the range of θ to negative values to include rays that traverse the lens on its opposite side.

Figure 2.5: A bend angle diagram for a typical spherical lens. The deflection rises linearly within the core of the lens until it begins to fall off as $1/r$ at larger radii. The intersections of the line L with the bend angle curve determine the image positions θ_A , θ_{B1} and θ_{B2} . The undeflected source position is θ_S .

2.4.3 The odd image theorem

It has been shown by Burke (1981) that for a transparent, non-singular mass distribution, the number of images of a source for any observer is always odd. To illustrate this different constraint lines (L_A , L_B and L_S) are drawn in the bend angle diagram shown in Figure 2.6. Evidently there are only three types of solution: those with one image represented by line L_A , those with three images represented by line L_B and the singular case represented by L_S . The latter solution is a special case and is discussed later in

We can also deduce a critical surface density of matter, Σ_{crit} for multiple imaging,

$$\Sigma \approx \frac{M}{4\pi r_C^2} \approx \frac{\alpha}{r_c} \frac{c^2}{16\pi G} \quad (2.33)$$

and using relation 2.32 we find,

$$\Sigma_{crit} \approx 1 \text{ g cm}^{-2}$$

These conditions are satisfied by most galaxies (with typical cores of a few kpc) but not by clusters (with typical cores of ≈ 100 kpc). We conclude that in general galaxies can create multiple images but clusters cannot, due to their lower degree of central concentration.

2.4.5 The role of clusters in lensing

Although clusters may not be involved in the actual formation of multiple images they still have a significant role to play in some lensed systems. In Figure 2.7, the bend angle function is drawn for a galaxy (α_g) and a cluster (α_c). The gradient of α_c is constant within the region shown here – the inner core of the cluster. The combined effect of the cluster and galaxy is shown as α_{gc} . We note that under favourable conditions the maximum separation, θ_{cl} , between the images is roughly doubled in comparison to the isolated galaxy case. The presence of a cluster of galaxies in addition to the main lensing galaxy, can noticeably increase the separation between the images.

2.4.6 Image amplification and parity

An important property of gravitational lensing is the conservation of surface brightness (Etherington 1933). Lens systems can produce images which are amplified, the amplification being the ratio of solid angle covered by the image relative to that of the source.

In practice the amplification of the images can be found by varying the source position, $\bar{\theta}_S$, over a small region $\delta\bar{\theta}_S$ and finding the corresponding image variation, $\delta\bar{\theta}_I$. Following Falco, Gorenstein & Shapiro (1985) differentiation of equation 2.4 yields,

$$\delta\bar{\theta}_S = \delta\bar{\theta}_I - \frac{D_{AS}}{D_{OS}} [A] \delta\bar{\theta}_I \quad (2.34)$$

or

$$\delta\bar{\theta}_S = \left([I] - \frac{D_{AS}}{D_{OS}} [A] \right) \delta\bar{\theta}_I = [M]^{-1} \delta\bar{\theta}_I \quad (2.35)$$

Figure 2.7: The effect of a cluster of galaxies on the image separations.

where $[A]$ is the partial derivatives of $\bar{\alpha}(\bar{\theta}_I)$ with respect to $\bar{\theta}_I$, $[I]$ is the identity matrix and $[M]$ is the absolute magnification matrix, which is always symmetric.

The amplification, Amp , which is the ratio of the projected area of the image to that of the source is given by

$$Amp = \frac{1}{\text{Det}([M]^{-1})} \quad (2.36)$$

If $\text{Det}([M]^{-1})$ is positive then the image is said to have positive parity, if it is negative it is said to have negative parity (i.e. it is mirror reversed).

The main points of this discussion are illustrated in Figure 2.8. We take an extended source $\theta_S \rightarrow \theta_S + \delta\theta_S$ in the form of an arc and construct the image positions using the bend angle diagram. The amplification of each image is just the ratio of the image to source areas. The image parities are obtained by labelling the sides of the source and noting where each side appears in the image. In Figure 2.8 image A has positive parity, while B1 and B2 have negative parities. In practice, the relative parities may be established from observations of the image structure. This is only possible for

those images which do exhibit such structure. In fact the only lens system to do so is 0957+561 A,B. VLBI observations of the core-jet structure in each of the images (made by Gorenstein, Cohen, Shapiro, Rogers, Bonometti, Falco, Bartel & Marcaide, 1988, hereafter GOR88) has allowed the image parities to be determined.

The magnification matrix for a double lens can be derived similarly, by differentiating equations 2.6 and 2.7. In the double lens case the magnification matrix involves the product of two symmetric matrices, hence, it is in general not symmetric (Blandford & Kochanek 1987). The main consequence of this is that it is not possible to reduce two lens planes to a single one with an appropriate mass distribution.

2.4.7 Caustics and critical lines

For a particular lens model and source position $Det([M]^{-1})$ can vanish, i.e. the image amplifications diverge to infinity. In the image plane the lines at which $Det([M]^{-1}) = 0$ are called *critical curves*. Their projections onto the source plane are known as the *caustics* of the lens. These caustics and critical lines can provide useful insights into the imaging characteristics of the lens e.g. Narayan (1988) and Narayan & Grossman (1989). As well as one dimensional *folds* there may be singular points on the caustic line, known as *cusps*. An elliptical lens with a finite core radius will have two caustics which divide the source plane into regions of different image multiplicities - one, three and five. As the source is moved across a fold two images will appear or disappear depending on the direction of the source motion. As one would expect, the brightness of the images changes rapidly during such a crossing. With cusps the situation is rather different, crossings result in either three bright images when the source is inside the cusp or a single bright image when the source is outside the cusp. If several lens masses are present an irregular pattern of caustics and critical lines are generated.

Caustic structure can also be understood in terms of a bend angle diagram. Referring back to Figure 2.6, it may be recalled that the solution given by line L_S was considered a special case. In fact it is possible to show that when the line $L(\theta)$ is tangential to the curve $\alpha(\theta)$, the intercept of the line locates the position of the caustic. At this point the source is exactly coincident with a caustic and the lens equation is no longer invertible (since $Det([M]^{-1})$ has diverged). In this region the lens system jumps discontinuously from a one image system to a three image system.

Figure 2.8: A bend angle diagram (top) for a spherical symmetric mass distribution can be used to construct a representation of the imaging of an object of radial extent $\delta\theta_S$.

2.5 The time delay

It can be seen from Figure 2.1 that the presence of the lens alters the time taken for light to reach the observer. This results in a time lag $\Delta\tau$ existing between the images. Cooke & Kantowski (1975) express the delay in terms of two components:

- a geometrical term, τ_{geom} , since bent ray paths are longer than direct lines of sight
- a potential term, τ_{pot} , arising from the gravitational potential of the lens.

For a system of n lenses located at different distances from the observer the time delay for one particular image is given by

$$c\tau = \sum_{i=1}^n (1 + z_i) \left(\frac{1}{2} (\bar{\theta}_{i+1} - \bar{\theta}_i)^2 \frac{D_{oi+1} D_{oi}}{D_{ii+1}} - \frac{2\phi_i(\bar{\theta}_i)}{c^2} \right) \quad (2.37)$$

where the $(n+1)^{th}$ screen is the source plane, and ϕ_i is the Newtonian potential at the intersection of the ray with the i^{th} screen. The first term in equation 2.37 is the geometrical term and the second is the potential term. This latter effect is well established by radar-ranging experiments in the solar system (Shapiro *et al.* 1971).

We can obtain the time lag between two images ($\bar{\theta}_A$ and $\bar{\theta}_B$, say) by determining equation 2.37 for each image and then subtracting i.e.

$$\Delta\tau_{AB} = (\tau_B - \tau_A)_{geom} + (\tau_B - \tau_A)_{pot} \quad (2.38)$$

We note that equation 2.37 can be written in such a way (Borgeest, & Refsdal 1984) that $\Delta\tau$ depends only on the lens model, the redshift of the lenses and the image positions *but not* Hubble's constant H_0 and *not* the cosmological model. For this reason a measurement of $\Delta\tau$ can be an important constraint on the lens mass distribution.

2.6 Micro-lensing

Thus far we have assumed that the surface mass density (lens mass distribution) varies as a smooth function of impact parameter. However, since a large fraction of the mass of galaxies is made up of stellar and possibly sub-stellar objects this cannot be strictly true. If for example one views a compact source through stars or other compact objects in an intervening galaxy, then these can act as 'micro-lenses' — splitting the main macro-images into several micro-images. Chang & Refsdal (1979) were the first

to consider the effect of the graininess of lensing galaxies on their associated macro-images.

Although the separation between the macro-images is only $\approx 10^{-6}$ arcseconds the amplification of each macro-image can be considerable. Under favourable conditions the amplification can be of the order of a few magnitudes. One can understand this by observing that the amplification is not dependent on the image separation but on the derivatives of α with respect to θ . The ripple effect shown in Figure 2.9 can lead to derivatives which are associated with strong amplification.

It is also clear that the amplification is also dependent on the size of the source. If the source and therefore its associated light bundle is sufficiently large, then only a small fraction of the bundle will be micro-lensed and any amplification effect will go unnoticed. Hence, the requirement for the angular size of the source is

$$\theta_{src} < \theta_{ER} \quad (2.39)$$

for significant micro-lensing. Because there exists a relative transverse velocity, V_T , between the source, observer and lensing mass the amplification should change on a time scale of

$$t_A \leq \frac{a_{ER}}{V_T} \quad (2.40)$$

Taking $V_T \approx 1000 \text{ kms}^{-1}$, $M \approx 0.2 M_\odot$ this implies $t_A \approx 4$ years.

Perhaps a more interesting case are the so called high amplification events or HAE for short. These occur when the source (radius R_{src}) crosses a caustic. As HAE are eclipse-like, their characteristic time scale is proportional to the source size:

$$t_{HAE} = \frac{2R_{src}}{V_T} \quad (2.41)$$

If $R_{SRC} \approx 10^{-4}$ pc (roughly the expected size for the optical continuum of a quasar) then typically $t_{HAE} \approx 0.2$ years. Kayser, Refsdal & Stabell (1986) estimate that for lensed quasars such as 0957+561, one can expect 1 HAE to occur over a period of 3 years. If one is fortunate enough to observe a HAE it may be possible to deduce the brightness profile of the source. In particular, as noted by Chang & Refsdal (1984), a double source should show up as two peaks in the light curve.

One further quirk of micro-lensing is the introduction of indirect chromatic effects. As we have discussed, micro-lensing is stronger for compact sources than for extended sources. Hence, if micro-lensing is at work, one would expect the quasar continuum to

be more affected than the emission line region. Also, since macro-images are observed through different parts of the galaxy, some images will be more affected by microlensing than others. In short, differences in spectra between macro-images need not automatically rule out gravitational lensing.

Figure 2.9: The graininess of galaxies results in a ripple being imposed on the otherwise smooth bend angle function

Chapter 3

Previous Studies of 0957+561

The problem in question, however, takes on a radically different aspect, if, instead of in terms of stars we think in terms of *extragalactic nebulae*. Provided that our present estimates of the masses of *cluster nebulae* are correct, the probability that nebulae which act as gravitational lenses will be found becomes practically a *certainty*. — Zwicky(1937b)

3.1 Introduction

With the announcement by Walsh, Carswell & Weymann (1979) (hereafter WCW) that 0957+561 A,B (often referred to as the 'double quasar') might be two images of a single quasar formed by a gravitational lens, astronomers around the world began to train their telescopes on this startling new phenomena. Needless to say, considerable amounts of observing and computing time have been devoted to this system. In this chapter we summarize the main observational and lens modelling results which have arisen over the last ten years.

3.2 Emission and absorption line spectra

In their discovery paper, WCW observed that the spectra of 0957+561 A,B had the following remarkable properties:

- strikingly similar spectra with identical emission line redshifts ($z_{em} = 1.405$) derived from the strongest spectral features CIV and CIII]
- good agreement in the equivalent widths of the CIV and CIII] lines
- absorption line systems with indistinguishable redshifts ($z_{obs} = 1.390$)

Figure 3.1 shows the spectra of 0957+561 A,B obtained by WCW. As noted by WCW the shape of the continuum is identical until about 5300 Å above which the flux of B rises more steeply than that of A. WCW explained this in terms of differential

Figure 3.1: Spectra obtained by WCW of 0957+561 A (top) and B (bottom). The two strong emission lines are CIV and CIII] (after Walsh *et al.* 1979).

extinction between the two light paths, caused by the presence of an intervening galaxy, presumably the lens itself.

Further observations by Weymann *et al.* (1979), Wills & Wills (1980) and Young, Sargent, Boksenberg & Oke (1981, hereafter YSBO) repeated WCW's original experiment but with much higher resolution and signal-to-noise. All three groups were able to confirm to high accuracy that there was no measurable velocity difference, $V_{em}(A-B)$, between the corresponding emission lines. Their results are summarised in table 3.1. Each of the three groups made similar measurements of the absorption line systems. The results are summarized in table 3.2.

Clearly the velocity differences between A and B for both the absorption and emission lines is extremely small. However, YSBO noticed that there appeared to be slight but real differences in structure between the absorption systems of the A and B images. This

is only to be expected since each of the image ray paths must travel through different regions of the absorbing medium. In fact, it is perhaps surprising that the systems appear to be so similar. YSBO also discovered a second absorption system at $z_{obs} = 1.1249$. Again the the velocity difference for this system is small $V_{obs}(A - B) = -8 \pm 11 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. The presence of similar absorption line systems with very small velocity differences was in itself, able to rule out the early 'binary quasar' hypothesis.

Group	$V_{em}(A-B) \text{ (km s}^{-1}\text{)}$	Emission Line(s)
Weymann <i>et al.</i>	-50 ± 50	Mg II
Wills & Wills	0 ± 400	CIII],MgII average
YSBO	25 ± 37	C IV

Table 3.1: List of velocity differences (A-B) between measured emission lines

Group	$V_{abs}(A-B) \text{ (km s}^{-1}\text{)}$	Absorption Systems
Weymann <i>et al.</i>	7 ± 15	Fe II, Mg II
Wills & Wills	3 ± 14	Fe II, Mg II
YSBO	8 ± 8	C IV, Si II, Fe II
	19 ± 11	As above excluding weakest C IV line

Table 3.2: List of velocity differences (A-B) between measured absorption lines

The nature of both absorption systems is still unclear. They may arise from one of three possibilities:

- intervening galaxies
- clouds of material ejected by the QSO
- intergalactic clouds at cosmological distances

All three have some associated disadvantage. One possible scenario is that the $z = 1.3911$ absorption system is due to a galaxy lying in a rich cluster of which the QSO is a member. The second absorption system might then be produced by a cloud ejected from the QSO itself.

In summary, the optical observations strongly supported WCW's original gravitational lens explanation for the double quasar.

3.3 Early radio observations

The first high resolution radio maps were produced by Pooley *et al.* (1979) and Roberts, Greenfield & Burke (1979). The map of Pooley *et al.* (1979) is shown in Figure 3.2. Both maps revealed two radio images of roughly equal brightness corresponding to the

Figure 3.2: Cambridge 5 km array map at 6 cm of the double quasar 0957+561 A,B. Contours are drawn at intervals of 4 mJy, negative contours are shown as dashed lines. Positions of the optical QSO's are marked by crosses (after Pooley *et al.* 1979)

optical cores A and B. There was no evidence of radio emission from any lens that might lie between the two. However, they did discover two steep spectrum jets north east and south west of A with no apparent counter parts at B.

The discovery of this complicated structure was difficult to reconcile with what at that time seemed reasonable lens models i.e. a point mass deflector positioned midway between A and B. Indeed, Roberts, Greenfield & Burke (1979) concluded that although gravitational lensing could not be ruled out, the new radio observations tended to suggest that the source was a true physical double, with the A component caught in the act of ejecting a relativistic plasma. Pooley *et al.* (1979) noted that although the steep spectrum jets were difficult to understand in terms of the conventional lensing hypothesis it could not be ruled out. Indeed, they noted that the coincidence of two

radio components of comparable flux with the optical QSO's was completely consistent with the lensing interpretation.

The objections raised by the radio maps, coupled with the differences in the A and B spectra at longer wavelengths, cast some doubt on the gravitational lens interpretation of 0957+561 A,B. It was not long however, until such doubts proved to be unfounded.

3.4 The discovery of the lensing galaxy

Shortly after the first radio results were published, Young *et al.* (1980) and independently Stockton (1980) obtained conclusive proof that the southern B image was being seen through a giant elliptical galaxy, designated 'G1'. Lying roughly one arcsecond North of the B image, it was observed by Young *et al.* (1980) to be just one of a rich cluster of galaxies in the field of view, albeit the brightest one.

By subtracting a scaled version of image A from image B, both Young *et al.* (1980) and Stockton (1980) were able to derive the distribution of light in the galaxy. Figure 3.3 shows the faint extension of the B image due to G1 and the results of the scaled subtraction.

Young *et al.* (1980) applied the same subtraction technique to the spectra of A and B, from which they were able to estimate a redshift of $z = 0.39 \pm 0.02$ for the galaxy. Armed with improved spectra YGKOW further refined this to $z = 0.36 \pm 0.01$. Stockton, whose observations were made under the exceptional seeing conditions of Mauna Kea ($\approx 0.5''$) was able to derive a position of 0.19 ± 0.03 east and 1.00 ± 0.03 arcseconds north for the galaxy (relative to image B). It should be noted that the galaxy is offset from the exact line joining the A and B images. This 'dog leg' is an important lens modelling constraint.

Stockton (1980) was also able to derive a core radius for the galaxy of 0.24 ± 0.09 arcseconds. Similarly, Young *et al.* (1980) measured its ellipticity to be 0.13 ± 0.01 at a position angle of 53 ± 5 (north through east). Neither Young *et al.* (1980) or Stockton (1980) detected any evidence of a third image, allowing Stockton to place an upper limit of 2% of the intensity of the B image on any third image lying close to the galaxy.

3.4.1 The rich cluster surrounding 0957+561 A,B

From their deep CCD frames (covering a 12.3 square arcminute field) YGKOW were able to compile a list of 180 objects (including the two QSO images) down to a limiting

Figure 3.3: To the left an integrated (300s) exposure of 0957+561 A,B. Note the northerly extension of image B. The extension in both images at position angle $\approx 240^\circ$ is caused by an artefact of imperfect telescope optics. To the right a scaled version of the A image has been subtracted from the B image revealing for the first time the lensing galaxy (after Stockton 1980).

magnitude of $r = 24.5$. By fitting profiles to each of these objects they were able to classify 32 as stars, and 146 as galaxies. The brightest galaxies showed a marked concentration towards the cluster core near G1. They also found that the cluster appeared to be appreciably flattened with core radii $50'' \times 27''$, the major axis lying east-west (position angle $\approx 90^\circ$).

YGKOW also attempted to determine the centre of mass of the cluster. By assuming that luminosity and mass are perfectly correlated they worked out the cluster centre by determining the centre of luminosity. Without spectroscopic confirmation YGKOW were unable to determine which galaxies were actually cluster members and which were foreground or background objects. They did not place any errors on the cluster centre they derived, but they must be fairly large. Including all the galaxies they obtained a cluster centre (x_c, y_c) (relative to B and adopting the coordinate system of chapter 2):

$$x_c = -36.3'' \text{ and } y_c = 1.9''$$

YGKOW began taking spectra of the brighter galaxies but stopped short at G5. They

found G2 was definitely a cluster member while G3 and G5 were probably not. Excluding G3 and G5 the centre becomes:

$$x_c = -21.9'' \text{ and } y_c = 3.4''$$

Clearly, the cluster centre thus determined is very sensitive to which bright galaxies are included and which are not. As we shall see in a later section the need for further spectral measurements in order to better determine the cluster centre was accelerated by the findings of early lens modelling programs.

3.5 Further observations

Measurements have also been made of the double quasar in the infrared (IR) and ultraviolet (UV) regions of the spectrum.

Soifer *et al.* (1980) detected extended IR emission in the vicinity of QSO B whose strength increased at longer wavelengths. They interpreted this as being due to the lensing galaxy identified by Young *et al.* (1980). By separating out the light distribution of the QSO's and the galaxy they were able to show that the ratio of the IR flux densities of the two QSO's (B/A) were the same (0.80 ± 0.15 at $1.65\mu\text{m}$ and 0.74 ± 0.15 at $2.2\mu\text{m}$) as that found at visual and radio wavelengths.

Similar results were reported by Lebofsky *et al.* (1980). Their estimates of the magnitude of the galaxy at K ($2.2\mu\text{m}$) placed it within the giant elliptical luminosity range. Both groups noted that the observed energy distribution of the QSO's were the same and extremely unusual for quasars - the spectra being remarkably flat from the IR to optical wavelengths. Soifer *et al.* (1980) stated that this made QSO A and B more similar to each other than any other known quasars.

The images of QSOA and QSOB are sufficiently bright to be observed with the International Ultraviolet Explorer satellite (IUE). Ultraviolet spectra of 0957+561 A,B were obtained by Gondhalekar & Wilson (1980). Both QSO's showed $\text{Ly}\alpha$ ($1216\text{\AA}$) in emission and absorption with redshifts consistent with the values determined in the optical i.e. $z_{em} = 1.41$ and $z_{obs} = 1.39$. They calculated that the flux ratios in the UV and radio (Roberts *et al.* 1979, Pooley *et al.* 1979) were almost unity. As well as agreeing with the simple predictions of the lens theory this result also implied that the two light paths must be almost extinction free.

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3.6 High resolution radio observations

Since the early maps of Pooley *et al.* (1979) and Roberts, Greenfield & Burke (1979) progress made in the areas of image reconstruction and instrumentation has allowed maps to be made of unprecedented angular resolution and sensitivity. Here, we discuss more recent radio observations of 0957+561 which have exploited these advances.

3.6.1 VLBI observations

Very soon after the discovery of the gravitational lens system 0957+561 A,B, VLBI observations using the European VLBI network (EVN) at $\lambda 18$ cm revealed compact structure in the lensed radio components A and B (Porcas *et al.* 1979). More extensive observations in February 1980 enabled Porcas *et al.* (1981) to discover the basic core-jet structure of the A and B images. Model-fitting elliptical Gaussian components to the visibility functions resulted in parameters for the core-jet separations and position angles as shown in table 3.3.

	Separation (mas)	Pos. angle $^{\circ}$
Image A	46 ± 1	21 ± 1
Image B	56 ± 2	17 ± 1

Table 3.3: The core-jet separations determined by Porcas *et al.* (1981).

The discovery of similar core-jet structure lent considerable weight to the lensing interpretation for 0957+561 A,B. However, as noted by Porcas *et al.* (1981) the close similarity of the separations and position angles could hardly have been predicted. To understand this recall Figure 2.8 of the previous chapter. Here we presented the imaging of a source line element by a spherically symmetric deflector. Since the line elements in images A and B1 of Figure 2.8 both point in the same direction we can identify QSO A and QSO B with these images. Note however, that the position angles of the line elements, far from being almost parallel (as observed in the VLBI core-jet structure), appear in different quadrants. Porcas *et al.* (1981) could only explain this result by assuming that the lens mass distribution must be non-spherically symmetric. With this and the previous dog leg result it became clear that only non-spherical lens masses would be able to reproduce all the observations.

Higher resolution (≈ 3.4 mas) $\lambda 13$ cm VLBI observations made by GORSS require four Gaussian components (two compact components — core and 'jet 1' separated by

≈ 3.3 mas, two extended components ≈ 50 mas from the core, 'jet 2' and 'jet 3') to describe the radio brightness distribution of each of the A and B images. A model plot of these features is shown in Figure 3.4. From these models GOR88 were able to confirm that the A and B images have opposite parity, albeit at the least significant contour level. For example jet 2 appears to the left of jet 3 in image A but to the right of jet 3 in image B. GOR88 also demonstrated that the brightness distributions

Figure 3.4: Contour plots of the four component gaussian models which represent the A and B images. Note the similarity in shape of the images, except for an expected parity inversion. The main characteristic of this parity inversion between the images is that 'jet 2' appears on opposite sides of 'jet 3's major axis. Note also that jet 1 curves in each image curve in different directions (after GOR88).

of the jet components in one image could be related to those in the other by a 2×2 magnification matrix.

This correspondence and the evidence for a change in parity from one image to the other all support the hypothesis that A and B are images of a single object. As we shall see in section 3.9, the VLBI observations have proved to be particularly important in constraining lens mass models.

3.6.2 VLA and MERLIN observations

A recent MERLIN map (kindly provided by T.W.B. Muxlow) of 0957+561 is shown in Figure 3.5. This is similar to VLA maps published by Roberts *et al.* (1985) with a

Figure 3.5: MERLIN 13 cm map of 0957+561. The faint bridge of emission seen between B and G1 is interpreted as being the only section of the north easterly jet that is multiply imaged. The peak flux is 43.9 mJy/beam. Contours are at -1, -0.5, -0.25, 0.25, 0.5, 1, 2, 4, 8, 12, 16, 20, 24, 28, 32, 36, 40 mJy/beam.

resolution of $0.35''$. The components A and B coincide with the optical image, extended components C, D, Jet and E together with A form an image of the object source. The component labelled G is believed to be radio emission from the main lensing galaxy G1.

The nature of the lens mass distribution, coupled with the VLBI observations, led to the abandonment of the minimal point source and spherically symmetric lens models. With the introduction of more realistic models (see 3.9 for details) it became possible

to understand the complicated radio structure in terms of the lensing hypothesis. The current view is that the undeflected QSO must lie close to a caustic which divides the source plane into regions of single and triple imaging. The MERLIN map shows an extension of the B quasar that is interpreted as the only part of the north easterly jet to fall within the multiply imaged region.

3.7 Search for the third image

As noted by Burke (1981) a transparent non-singular gravitational lens will produce an odd number of images. Most lens models of 0957+561 predict that a dim third image should lie near the core of the main lensing galaxy G1. In an attempt to detect this so far elusive third image, Gorenstein *et al.* (1983) used their March 1981 $\lambda 13$ cm data to search a region $0.2''$ north, $0.2''$ east, $0.2''$ west and $0.6''$ south of the VLA position for G. From their most sensitive Madrid–Goldstone baseline they detected a compact component (< 0.002 mas) labelled G' with a flux of 0.6 mJy at position $0.181''$ east and $1.029''$ north of the VLBI core of the B image. In table 3.4 the measured positions of G1, G, and G' are presented.

Object	Identification	Position (RA, DEC) rel. to B (epoch 1950.0)
G1	Optical (Stockton 1980)	$(0.19 \pm 0.03 \ 1.00 \pm 0.03)$
G	VLA (Roberts 1985)	$(0.151 \pm 0.001 \ 1.051 \pm 0.001)$
G'	VLBI (Gorenstein <i>et al.</i>)	$(0.181 \pm 0.001 \ 1.029 \pm 0.001)$

Table 3.4: Positions of G1, G and G' relative to B

G' was subsequently detected at $\lambda 3.8$ cm and $\lambda 6$ cm (Bonometti 1985 and Rogers 1989). Table 3.5 summarizes the strength (relative to the total flux of the core of the B image) of this component on the Goldstone–Madrid (GM) and VLA–Bonn (VB) baselines.

Date of observation	Baseline	G' at 13 cm	G' at 3.8 cm	G' at 6 cm
March 1981	GM	$B_{core}/36$	-	-
May 1983	GM	$B_{core}/18$	$B_{core}/10$	-
July 1983	VB	-	-	$B_{core}/30$

Table 3.5: Flux strengths of G' at 3.8, 6, 13 cm with respect to the B image

Until recently the general consensus (Walsh 1983, Hewitt 1986) was that G' was probably emission from the core of the main lensing galaxy $G1$, rather than the faint third image of the quasar. This was the favoured explanation for two main reasons:

- $G1$ and G' appear to be nearly coincident but lens models predict that the third image should lie ≈ 100 mas south of B .
- Bonometti (1985) showed that the flux variations of B and G measured by the VLA over a period of two years were different. In addition, their radio spectra were also different.

Figure 3.6: The hybrid map of G' made from the VLB data of GOR88 (after Rogers 1989)

However, Rogers (1989) has reported that a hybrid map (made from $\lambda 13$ cm 1981 VLB data) of this component suggests the presence of a 'jet' located ≈ 8 mas due south of G' , with a signal-to-noise ratio of 3. The map is shown in Figure 3.6. The visibility data are consistent with a lens model by Bonometti (1985), which assumed G' was the third image.

Rogers (1989) also argues that the increase in flux of G' from March 1981 to May 1983 (see table 3.5) by a factor of two may be explained by micro-lensing. Micro-lensing might also be responsible for the spectral index differences between G' and the other images. Until more sensitive observations are made, the true nature of G' remains uncertain.

3.8 Time delay measurements

As discussed in section 2.5 there is a time delay between the arrival of radiation from two images formed by a gravitational lens. It soon became clear that a determination of $\Delta\tau_{AB}$ would not only be of value to lens models but would also be definitive proof that A and B really are two images of a distant QSO. In principle, the light curves of 0957+561 A,B should differ only by a magnification ratio, R , and the time delay $\Delta\tau_{AB}$. This idealised picture must be modified, however, because of the effects of micro-lensing.

The earliest reports of flux variations in 0957+561 A,B were made by Lloyd (1981) and Keel (1982). They found that optical variations of ≈ 0.1 magnitude occurred on the time scale of months. Variability of several hundredths of a magnitude appear to have been observed by Vanderreist *et al.* (1982) and Schild & Chofin (1986) over a few days. As for long term changes, analysis of archive plates suggest that both QSO's may have been at least 0.5 magnitudes brighter around the turn of the century.

Frequent monitoring of 0957+561 A,B has been conducted at optical ultraviolet and radio wavelengths. Here we summarize the progress made in each of these areas.

3.8.1 Optical monitoring

Unfortunately, optical observations are interrupted for approximately half the year by the sun. This and the relatively quiescent state of 0957+561 has resulted in 'light' curves which are fairly bland and hence difficult to correlate.

The first published value for a time delay between the A and B images of 0957+561 was made by Florentin-Nielsen (1984). Taking repeated photographs of 0957+561 with a twenty inch Schmidt camera, they observed a 0.3^m brightening in A which was followed by a brightening in B about one and a half years later. From this 'event' Florentin-Nielsen (1984) derived a delay $\Delta\tau_{AB} = 1.55 \pm 0.1$ years (A leading). However, the published light curves are not convincing, the individual scatter of the points are almost of the same order as the labelled fluctuation. No statistical analysis was given and no later publication, giving a more complete time series has appeared.

Vanderreist *et al.* (1989) have published what is probably the most complete data set, obtained from a variety of sources. Figure 3.7 shows the light curves they obtained for both images. Part of this data set uses observations made by Schild & Chofin (1986). Indeed it is the same 0.2^m dip which led Schild to suggest a delay of 1.03 ± 0.1

Figure 3.7: Light curves of the two QSO images (after Vanderriest *et al.* 1989).

years, that remains the main feature of the light curves presented by Vanderriest *et al.* (1989).

Cross-correlation of the light curves yields a maximum at $\Delta\tau_{AB} \approx 419 \pm 30$ days. Restricting the correlation to the period 1983-1986 gives a correlation coefficient of ≈ 0.8 . However, if the same procedure is applied to each of the individual data sets (data obtained from the same instrument) $\Delta\tau_{AB}$ is in the range 390-440 days with substantially lower coefficients (0.2-0.5). We also note that the amplitude of the variation is not so much greater than that seen on very short ($\approx$ days) time scales. These differences may be due to the difficulty in performing absolute photometry on the closely spaced images and are probably a good indication of the measurement errors.

3.8.2 IUE monitoring

A series of UV observations using the IUE satellite have been reported by Gondhalekar *et al.* (1986). These were limited in time by aspect considerations for the spacecraft and by observing seasons. Eleven observations were made from the period 1980 to 1983, during which a dip in the flux of A was followed by a similar dip in B. It must be said that the light curves do not look particularly convincing.

This event gives a formal time delay $\Delta\tau_{AB}$ of 1.8 ± 0.2 years. Again, one would wish for a longer series of data before this result can be given much weight.

3.8.3 VLA monitoring

Figure 3.8: VLA light curves of the two QSO images (after Lehár *et al.* 1989).

In principle the radio data can give a more definitive value for the time delay since the effects of micro-lensing are likely to be less pronounced at radio wavelengths. However, the flux variations at radio wavelengths are even smaller than those observed in the optical and they occur more slowly. Lehár, Hewitt & Roberts (1989) have made 65 snapshots of 0957+561 at $\lambda 6$ cm with the VLA, from 1981 to 1989. The data were taken in the more extended (higher resolution) configurations of the VLA. Even so in the B configuration the B image was contaminated by the radio emission from the jet and G. Like the optical monitoring, the VLA observations are only possible for only part of the year due to changes in the array configuration.

Both images (see figure 3.8) showed a steady decrease in brightness for the first few years, but by 1984 the flux of A increased significantly, declining thereafter at a slower rate. The flux of B continued its decline until early 1985 when it also increased in flux. Lehár, Hewitt & Roberts (1989) estimate that the delay is between 400 and 600 days although the best fit is for 483 days and a flux ratio $R=1.448$.

3.8.4 Discussion

The optical and VLA derived time delays are just consistent with each other. The time delay obtained from IUE measurements is consistent with the VLA result but not the optical result. It is highly probable that all three light curves are affected to some extent by micro-lensing, even the radio observations. The amplification ratio, R , is considerably different ($R \approx 1$) in the optical than that measured by the flux ratio of the VLBI jet ($R \approx 0.64$). This implies that the optical continuum source is being enhanced by about 0.3^m in the B image. In addition, the periodic variation of the magnification ratio, R , noted by Vanderriest *et al.* (1989) is best explained by micro-lensing. In view of the fact that micro-lensing can masquerade as intrinsic source brightness variations and recalling that each of the derived time delays are dependent on one single 'event' it seems only prudent to consider the time delay results as provisional.

3.9 Previous lens modelling attempts

Extensive modelling studies have been carried out on the double quasar. Lens models must be able to account for

- the pronounced 'dog leg' in the observed A-G1-B positions
- the flux amplification ratio between the A and B images
- a dim third image no brighter than 1-2% of B
- all of the south-westerly and the greater part of the north-easterly jet being only singly imaged.
- the similar position angles for the VLBI core-jet structures seen in both images

Young *et al.* (1980) constructed the first detailed models in an attempt to explain the images seen. They represented the galaxy G1 and its associated cluster with spherically symmetric King (1966) distributions. Young *et al.* (1980) found that although the cluster alone could not form multiple images it severely complicated the imaging of the system. An early model which predicted that the B image was actually a close double can be ruled out by later VLBI observations.

Other models (YGKOW) in which G1 alone acted as the lens, required unreasonably large velocity dispersions (470 km s^{-1}) and ellipticities (0.6). YGKOW also constructed

models of the lens in which both the galaxy G1 and the cluster were represented by elliptically symmetric King (1966) model distributions. Individual cluster galaxies were represented by point masses. A large quantity of dark matter not associated with individual cluster members is implied by such double-ellipsoid models. Since each model has 10 adjustable parameters it might be thought that any set of observations could be fitted. However, YGKOW noted that fitting *either* the skew in the image line *or* the high brightness of B (w.r.t A) was relatively easy but fitting both "strained the capacity of the models". Moreover, YGKOW models were not constrained by the VLBI observations of Porcas *et al.* (1981).

Greenfield, Roberts & Burke (1985) extended upon this work by showing that those models in which the masses of G1 and the other galaxies were proportional to their luminosity did not work. Other models in which the mass-to-light ratio of the galaxies was assumed to be a linear function of luminosity fared no better. They obtained greater success by modeling the galaxy and cluster with elliptical King models. However, these so called 'double ellipsoid' models were not consistent with the VLBI results.

Similar models produced by Higgs (1984) and Narasimha, Subramanian & Chitre (1984) also suffer from defects. The latter group present two solutions, but both suffer from implausibly high values of R the flux ratio for B1/A (1.25, 1.22) The models of Higgs (1984) appear at first to be consistent with the data but as discussed in chapter 6, they are fatally flawed. Significantly, both Higgs (1984) and Narasimha, Subramanian & Chitre (1984) noted that the VLBI results could only be reproduced satisfactorily if the cluster centre was moved outside the range suggested by YGKOW 19-30 arcseconds west of G1, and brought closer to the galaxy centre.

The problem of non-uniqueness of models of individual systems for which observations do not allow a complete knowledge of the system has been considered by GOR88. It appears that information on the structure of the lens mass distribution can be particularly important.

Falco, Gorenstein & Shapiro (1988) have modelled 0957+561 A,B with G1 represented by a King model with a point like object at its centre. The cluster is represented by a simple linear deflector model. They use the VLBI data of Gorenstein, Falco & Shapiro (1988) to constrain the mass distribution of the lens. Again, anomalous mass distributions not related to conventional visible matter must be invoked. Unfortunately,

their model construction does not permit the calculation of image properties at impact parameters other than those for A and B.

Lens models of 0957+561 have been able to establish some important results. For example, it appears that dark matter is necessary to reproduce the image observables. This dark matter does not seem to be concentrated in the visible galaxies but rather distributed smoothly over the extent of the cluster. This in itself is strong evidence that dark matter is not associated directly with galaxies.

3.10 Summing up

In the years since its discovery, 0957+561 has been subject to intense observational scrutiny. These observations have provided overwhelming evidence that the double quasar is, without doubt, an example of gravitational lensing. For the time being it seems we must do without the time delay or the position and strength of the third image to further constrain lens models. Nevertheless, the work of Greenfield, Roberts & Burke (1985) has illustrated how strongly the relative orientations and separations of the VLBI core-jet structure can restrict model solutions. In addition, Higgs (1984) and Narasimha, Subramanian & Chitre (1984) have shown the need for an accurate determination of the cluster centre.

With these ideas in mind it seems likely that further progress can be made in two main directions:

- higher sensitivity MERLIN-VLBI observations of the A and B images
- a program of multi-slit spectroscopy to better determine the cluster centre.

These observations form the subject of the following two chapters.

Chapter 4

EVN observations of 0957+561

VLBI observations present a new set of constraints — P. Young.

4.1 Introduction

The discovery of similar core-jet structure in each of the A and B images of 0957+561 by Porcas *et al.* (1981) places a strong constraint on lens models of the system. As a result the double quasar has been a primary target for VLBI arrays for over a decade. However, until now the paucity of the data has meant that the observations have been analysed by the simple model fitting technique. In this chapter we present new observations made with the full European VLBI Network (EVN). These observations have allowed us to make the first VLBI hybrid maps of the A and B images (Porcas *et al.* 1989).

Although VLBI observations of sources can be regarded (at least in some sense) as 'routine' the data reduction path is often long and complicated. As we shall see, the double quasar by its very nature introduces its own specific problems to this area. We begin therefore by presenting an outline of the techniques associated with VLBI.

4.2 Very Long Baseline Interferometry

In the mid 1960's a new technique of interferometry was developed called Very Long Baseline Interferometry (VLBI). This technique allows the use of widely separated telescopes as elements of a high resolution interferometer array. The scientific motivation for the development of VLBI came from the realization that many radio sources had structures which could not be resolved by interferometers with baselines of a few hundred kilometers. It was also well known that time variability of the radiation from quasars implied angular sizes of < 0.01 arcsecond. Hence, the aim of the first VLBI observations was to measure the angular sizes of these sources. During the first decade only crude images could be obtained, however by the late 1970's Readhead & Wilkinson

(1978), convincingly demonstrated the imaging potential of VLBI arrays, when they produced the first VLBI 'hybrid maps'.

Unlike other forms of radio interferometry (e.g. MERLIN) the large distances that separate each of the telescopes make it impractical to provide real-time links between the receiving elements. In VLBI the signals received at each telescope must be recorded on tape during the observing run. After the run has finished the recorded data tapes are sent to a central processing facility where they are correlated.

In Europe, VLBI observations are carried out by the European VLBI Network (EVN). The EVN is composed of individual telescopes belonging to various European radio astronomical institutes. During VLBI sessions these telescopes are coupled together to form an extremely sensitive array with a large resolving power. In conjunction with the United States VLBI Network (USVN), resolutions (of a few milliarcsecond) can be achieved that are unrivalled in any other branch of astronomy.

The basic principles of producing maps from VLBI data do not differ significantly from those employed in the case of short baseline interferometry arrays, such as MERLIN. The most important differences result from the use of separate frequency standards at each telescope and the difficulty in determining the geometry of the array accurately.

4.2.1 Radio interferometry

The theory of interferometry and aperture synthesis has been treated by various authors: e.g. Fomalont & Wright (1974), Thompson, Moran & Swenson (1986) and Spencer (1989). Here we present only a brief outline of the subject.

The two element interferometer (see figure 4.1) provides high resolution by combining the signals of the two telescopes in the correlator. The correlator multiplies the signals together and takes an average, over some specified time interval. The basic observables are then the correlated amplitude and the relative phase of waves from a common source at two points on the wavefront. These amplitudes and phases are known as the *visibilities*.

If the radiation source is effectively at infinity, in the direction of the unit vector $\vec{S}$, the signal arrives at the 'reference telescope' late by an amount

$$\tau_g = \frac{(\vec{B} \cdot \vec{S})}{c} = \frac{B}{c} (\sin \delta_S \sin \delta_B + \cos \delta_B \cos \delta_S \cos(H_S - H_B)) \quad (4.1)$$

where the baseline $\vec{B}$, runs from the reference telescope to the remote telescope, H_S

and δ_S are the hour angle and the declination of the source respectively, and H_B and δ_B are the hour angle and declination of the baseline vector $\vec{B}$ respectively.

The relative phase ϕ in radians of the signals received at each end of the baseline is

$$\phi = \omega\tau_g = 2\pi\nu\tau_g \quad (4.2)$$

where ν is the observing frequency.

Owing to the Earth's rotation, ϕ is changing at a rate F , known as the fringe rate:

$$F = \frac{d\phi}{dt} = \dot{\phi} = \frac{-2\pi B}{\lambda} \cos \delta_B \cos \delta_S \sin(H_S - H_B) \frac{dH_S}{dt} \quad (4.3)$$

The projection of the baseline $\vec{B}$ on the plane of the incident wavefront is given by the vector $\vec{b}$. This may be resolved into two components in the directions of right ascension (E-W) and declination (N-S) and are termed the u and v components respectively.

$$u = \frac{B}{\lambda} \cos \delta_B \sin(H_S - H_B) \quad (4.4)$$

$$v = \frac{B}{\lambda} (\sin \delta_B \cos \delta_S - \cos \delta_B \sin \delta_S \cos(H_S - H_B)) \quad (4.5)$$

As the Earth rotates the components of the projected baseline vary with the hour angle of the source. The resultant path of the projected baseline in the ' u - v ' plane, is useful in understanding the principles of aperture synthesis. If the reference telescope is considered to be fixed at the origin of the u - v plane, the other telescope will trace out an arc of an ellipse. If the source is observed for several hours, then a single baseline is able to record the correlated signal or visibility for a range of u and v points.

Consider an extended radio source (figure 4.1) with a brightness distribution $I(\vec{\sigma}, \nu)$. We can consider the source to be made up of a number of independent radiating sources with vector position, $\vec{\sigma}$, on the sky. The response of the interferometer sensitive to an observing bandwidth $\Delta\nu$ is given by

$$R(\vec{\sigma}, \nu) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{\nu_0 - \Delta\nu/2}^{\nu_0 + \Delta\nu/2} I(\vec{\sigma}, \nu) A(\vec{\sigma}, \nu) \cos 2\pi\nu\tau_g d\nu d\vec{\sigma} \quad (4.6)$$

where $A(\vec{\sigma})$ is the effective telescope area. It is a complicated function of $\vec{\sigma}$ known as the beam pattern. We continue by ignoring the dependence $I(\vec{\sigma}, \nu)$ and $A(\vec{\sigma}, \nu)$ on ν , and substituting equation 4.1 into relation 4.6. Then with a little reduction 4.6 can be

Figure 4.1: A typical connected interferometer pair

written in complex form:

$$R(\vec{\sigma}) = V A_0 \Delta\nu \exp\left(i\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \vec{B} \cdot \vec{\sigma}\right) = V A_0 \Delta\nu \exp(i\phi) \quad (4.7)$$

where

$$V = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} I(\vec{\sigma}) A'(\vec{\sigma}) \exp\left(i\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \vec{b} \cdot \vec{\sigma}\right) d\sigma. \quad (4.8)$$

and $A'(\vec{\sigma}) \equiv A(\vec{\sigma})/A_0$ is the normalised beam pattern, A_0 being the response at the beam centre.

We note that the response has a maximum when the phase $\phi = 2n\pi$, where n is an integral number. The spacing between maxima is the fringe angular spacing or the resolution of the interferometer. This spacing is

$$\frac{d\phi}{d\theta} = \frac{d}{d\theta} \left(\frac{2\pi B \cos \theta}{\lambda} \right) = -\frac{2\pi b}{\lambda} \quad (4.9)$$

where b is the projected baseline. The angular resolution, $\Delta\theta$ is just

$$\Delta\theta = \frac{\lambda}{b} \quad (4.10)$$

From the form of 4.8, the visibility function is obviously the Fourier transform of the brightness distribution. It is therefore possible to recover the source brightness distribution by performing the inverse Fourier transform:

$$I(\vec{\sigma}) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} V(\vec{b}) \exp(-i\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \vec{b} \cdot \vec{\sigma}) d\vec{b} \quad (4.11)$$

In practice it is convenient to use cartesian coordinates, where $\vec{\sigma} = (x, y)$ and $\vec{b} = (u, v)$ so that 4.11 becomes

$$I(x, y) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} V(u, v) \exp(-i\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}(ux + vy)) dx dy \quad (4.12)$$

Equation 4.12 is the fundamental equation of aperture synthesis. It tells us that if V is known for all values of u and v , the source brightness can be recovered uniquely. In practice V is known only for a limited number of (u, v) points. However, for an array of N telescopes there will be a maximum of $N(N-1)/2$ different baselines, enabling a relatively substantial u - v coverage to be obtained with only a few telescopes.

4.2.2 Practical considerations

In equation 4.3 we derived the fringe rate or fringe frequency one would expect to find with an interferometer pair. Placing some typical VLBI values into this equation gives fringe rates in the kHz range. It is therefore necessary to reduce the fringe rate so that the fringe output can be efficiently and properly sampled. In connected interferometry, this can be achieved by the addition of a varying local oscillator phase, ϕ_{LO} , into one arm of the interferometer. Thus in equation 4.1 $\phi = 2\pi\nu\tau_g - \phi_{LO}$. However, in VLBI this fringe stopping or fringe rotation as it is commonly known, must be controlled during the correlation of the data.

Since the signal arriving at each telescope must be amplified before being recorded on magnetic tape, the incoming radio frequency (RF) is mixed with a local oscillator signal (LO) to convert it to a lower more manageable intermediate frequency (IF). The LO must have sufficient stability to ensure that recorded VLBI signals can be cross correlated and still maintain coherence. In order to preserve fringe phase, the LO must be extremely stable (one part in 10^{13}). Such stability can be obtained by using hydrogen masers as frequency standards.

The use of these independent frequency standards at each telescope means that in VLBI (as compared to conventional connected arrays) one has less control over the stability of the system. Uncertainties in the clock offsets, geometry of the array and atmospheric effects, make it very difficult to predict accurately the delays and phases which will maximise the response of a VLBI interferometer pair. The result is the existence of residual delays and fringe rates. This means that a search must be made in fringe rate and delay space to find the strongest fringes. To reduce the area that must be searched a strong source (called a fringe finder) is observed during the observing run. Because of its strength it is relatively easy to find fringes. Once found the associated rates and delays can be used to define a narrower window within which fringes for the weaker source are likely to be found.

4.3 Image reconstruction

The use of self-calibration and deconvolution algorithms in iterative routines played an important part in transforming VLBI into the powerful imaging tool we take for granted today. Some useful references which address these and other related topics, can be found in Cornwell (1982), Ekers (1983), Pearson & Readhead (1984), Cornwell

& Wilkinson (1984) and Wilkinson (1989a,b). The following discussion is based on these treatments.

4.3.1 Utilising the closure phase information

A fundamental problem in VLBI is that the observed complex visibility, V , measured by any interferometer pair in a VLBI array, is severely corrupted by instrumental and propagation effects. In particular, the phase information is badly degraded by the use of separate clocks and local oscillators at each of the observing sites, and by the effect of the ionosphere and other regions of the atmosphere on the path of the radio signal itself. Without some way of retrieving the phase information it is impossible to deduce the source brightness distribution from equation 4.12.

It is perhaps not always obvious that the source phase information is just as important as the amplitude information. Baldwin & Warner (1978) have shown that a map made with the correct phase, but an amplitude of unity, bears more resemblance to the true map, than a map made with the correct amplitude and zero phase. Basically, the amplitude tells how bright a particular area is, and the phase tells where to place it. To produce realistic images from VLBI data the closure phase can be used to recover part of the phase information.

Let us consider three telescopes in an array: j , k and l . We shall ignore any noise terms that may be present. The source visibility has phases ψ_{jk} , ψ_{kl} and ψ_{jl} ; and the phase errors associated with each telescope are θ_j , θ_k and θ_l . Then summing the observed visibility phases ϕ_{jk} , ϕ_{kl} and ϕ_{jl} around this triangle of baselines, we observe that the telescope errors will cancel in the phase closure relation:

$$\phi_{jk} + \phi_{kl} - \phi_{jl} = (\psi_{jk} + \theta_j - \theta_k) + (\psi_{kl} + \theta_k - \theta_l) - (\psi_{jl} + \theta_j - \theta_l) = \psi_{jk} + \psi_{kl} - \psi_{jl} \quad (4.13)$$

Clearly, the phase errors associated with individual telescopes cancel out and we have an observable which contains information on the true visibility phase itself. The sources absolute positional information is lost, however.

Jennison (1953), discovered the phase closure relation while working on triple interferometer observations at Jodrell Bank. He used it in an attempt to retrieve phase information which had been badly corrupted by the poor stability of his equipment. Later, as interferometers became phase stable, the method fell into obscurity. It was only with the emergence of VLBI in the late 1960's and early 1970's that the method

was revived to take into account not only instrumental phase errors, but also phase errors associated with the propagation of the signal through the atmosphere.

4.3.2 CLEAN a deconvolution algorithm

Deconvolution algorithms were developed to correct for the presence of sidelobes in radio maps. The presence of sidelobes is found in any interferometric array, but their effect is particularly severe in the case of VLBI, where the u - v plane is poorly sampled. If we set the visibility, $V = 0$, at all points in the u - v plane where we have not measured data, and attempt to Fourier transform back to the sky plane, we get a distorted map or 'dirty map'. It can be shown that the 'dirty map' is just the 'true map' convolved with the so called 'dirty beam'. The 'dirty beam' is the Fourier transform of the sampling of the u - v plane.

In a procedure devised by Högbom (1974), the dirty map is numerically deconvolved with the dirty beam to produce a set of CLEAN components (or delta functions) which are representative of the source structure. The CLEANed map is obtained by convolving the CLEAN components with a CLEAN beam and adding any residual components. The CLEAN beam is normally chosen to be an elliptical gaussian with a beamwidth equal to the beamwidth of the original dirty beam $\approx \lambda/D$. It is possible to restrict CLEAN to particular areas of the map; this is called windowing. Windowing constrains the source brightness distribution which can fit the measured visibilities and should be used with care. Windowing emission due to artifacts or spurious symmetrization (Lindfield 1986) can lead to features in the map which are unreal e.g. counter jets.

4.3.3 Hybrid mapping

The first widely accepted iterative procedure using closure phase to produce VLBI maps, a technique known as hybrid mapping, was devised by Readhead & Wilkinson (1978) (hereafter RW). They reasoned that for an array of N telescopes there are $\frac{1}{2}N(N-1)$ visibility phases and $\frac{1}{2}(N-1)(N-2)$ independent closure phase relations. This leaves $N-1$ too few linear combinations to solve for all the visibility phases. To get round this problem RW made a guess at the true source brightness distribution of the source and from this model derived the missing $N-1$ visibility phases. Thus they were able to solve for the remaining visibility phases. They noted that the visibility phases derived in this way were thus consistent with the closure phases. RW added these visibilities to the $N-1$ model visibilities, fourier inverted and CLEANed them to

produce a 'hybrid map'. The output CLEAN components were then used as the next input model, and so the method continued until convergence was achieved i.e. the map failed to improve any further.

In most cases a point source starting model will suffice, though convergence is often speeded up by a more realistic brightness distribution. Maps produced in this way also make use of some simple assumptions about the image. For example, we assume that the sky brightness distribution cannot be negative (outwith the expected noise level) and that the source has a finite size. Also, experience has shown that a simple structure that fits the data is more likely to be correct than a complex structure that fits the data equally well. It is important during the mapping loop to compare the model derived from the CLEAN components with the observed visibilities.

The RW method works well for arrays in which the number of telescopes is small. As the number of telescopes increases, however, the number of possible closure phases is much larger, and problems such as computer time and storage arise. In response to this and other problems Schwab (1980) and Cornwell & Wilkinson (1981) devised the method of self-calibration, in which the closure relationships are obeyed implicitly rather than explicitly. This method of self-calibration has been implemented in the major software mapping packages used today.

4.4 Data acquisition

0957+561 A,B was observed at $\lambda 18$ cm by five stations of the EVN beginning at 07:56 UT on February 27 and ending on 06:15 UT on February 28, 1987. Details of the telescopes used are listed in table 4.1.

Observatory	Location	Diameter (m)	T_{ν} (Jy)	Freq. Standard
Effelsberg	FRG	100	30	H-maser
Jodrell Bank Lovell	UK	76	75	Rubidium
Westerbork Array	Netherlands	-	131	H-maser
Medicina	Italy	32	934	H-maser
Onsala	Sweden	25	491	H-maser

Table 4.1: Telescope characteristics

Since the two images A and B are separated by only six arcseconds simultaneous observations of both components were necessarily made at each telescope. The observations were made with the Mark III VLBI system recording in mode B (Rogers *et al.*

Figure 4.2: The Observed (u, v) coverage for the EVN observations of 0967+561.

1983). The bandwidth of the observations was therefore 28 MHz. There were no major problems at any station during the observing run. A calibration source 0917+624 was observed by each telescope at the same time on at least two separate occasions. These data were used to find a consistent calibration for all the telescopes. Figure 4.2 shows the actual u - v coverage of the observations.

4.5 Correlating the data

The MkIII tapes were correlated at the Max-Planck-Institut für Radioastronomie, (MPIfR), Bonn, using the three station MkIII processor. The data were correlated in the usual way - COREL (the correlator control program) and FRNGE (the program which searches the correlator output for the maximum response in residual fringe rate

and delay space) running in parallel. Since both the A and B images are within the primary beam of any individual telescope and since both are of similar strength FRNGE maximised the correlation output for the A image on some 13 minute scans and the B image on other scans. Figure 4.3 shows a graph of delay vs UT for the Jodrell Bank - Medicina baseline. The jumps in the graph occur when FRNGE switches from the A to the B image and vice-versa. In this form the correlated data cannot be used to produce a map, since the visibilities correspond to different parts of the source structure.

Figure 4.3: A graph of residual delay against UT for the Jodrell Bank - Medicina baseline. Note the jumps in the delay as the FRNGE program finds one image and then the other.

A solution to this problem (devised by R.W. Porcas) was obtained in the following way. Consider two sources separated by $\Delta\alpha_S$ and $\Delta\delta_S$. The estimated difference in the delay $\Delta\tau_g$ and rate $\Delta\dot{\phi}$ can be obtained by differentiating equations 4.1 and 4.3:

$$\Delta\tau_g = \frac{B}{c} (\cos\delta_B \cos\delta_S \sin(H_S - H_B) \cdot \Delta\alpha_S + (\sin\delta_B \cos\delta_S - \cos\delta_B \sin\delta_S \cos(H_S - H_B)) \cdot \Delta\delta_S) \quad (4.14)$$

$$\Delta\dot{\phi} = \frac{2\pi B}{\lambda} \cos\delta_B \frac{dH_S}{dt} (\cos\delta_S \cos(H_S - H_B) \cdot \Delta\alpha_S + \sin\delta_S \sin(H_S - H_B) \cdot \Delta\delta_S) \quad (4.15)$$

Knowing the relative separation between the components a small FORTRAN program was used to calculate $\Delta\tau_g$ and $\Delta\dot{\phi}$ between the components and this was then compared with the graphs. By identifying which component had been detected in any particular scan the program was used to calculate a rate and delay for the undetected component. Armed with these rates and delays the appropriate FRNGE parameter file was produced for each component. The data were then re-fringed using each of these parameter files. The end result was two data sets: one re-fringed on the A component, the other on the B component. The data were then coherently integrated for 2, 4 and 13 minutes. Thereafter all data reduction was performed at Jodrell Bank.

4.6 Reformatting the data into EVN120 format

Although the data had been requested in EVN120 format, MPIFR sent the data in 1701 format. The first job was therefore to reformat the data. A FORTRAN program was written to accomplish this task. The program also calculated formal errors for the visibilities, which were not included in the original 1701 data file. Once the data had been reformatted an EVN120 header (contains information on the station coordinates, position of source, frequency and polarisation of the observations) was appended to the top of the file¹. The resulting file was then transferred to the Caltech software package by the MERGE routine.

4.7 Editing and calibrating the data

Initial editing and calibration of the data was performed within the Caltech VLBI package. VLBEDIT was used to edit bad visibility points from the data. Such bad points were relatively few in number and were in most cases station-based errors.

The visibility amplitudes were calibrated to obtain correlated flux densities following Cohen (1975). Amplitude calibration involved converting the estimates of the fringe amplitudes from correlator units into Janskys. A correction is made for the loss in signal to noise, introduced by the one bit sampling and other correlator based effects. These factors are lumped together in a term known as the 'b factor'. Its value depends on which correlator has been used to correlate the data. For the MPIFR MkIII correlator $b \approx 1.0$. The formula for expressing the relationship between correlator units

¹EVN120 has several serious shortcomings and VLBI data should no longer be exported in this format. FITS is the format of choice in virtually all circumstances

and Janskys is

$$S(\text{Jy}) = b\rho\sqrt{\frac{T_1T_2}{G_1G_2}} \quad (4.16)$$

where $S(\text{Jy})$ is the calibrated, correlated flux density; b is the 'b factor', ρ is the raw correlator coefficient, T_i is the system temperature of the i^{th} telescope (in Kelvin) and G_i is the telescope gain - a function of elevation (K/Jy).

The receiver system temperatures (T_i) were monitored at each telescope throughout the observations and the gains (G_i) determined at each telescope from standard calibration sources. At most sites the gain is very nearly constant except at very low elevations.

The Caltech program CAL was used to calibrate the data. It required a file containing the measured system temperatures, telescope gains and baseline b - factors. The calibration was adjusted by applying it to the unresolved calibrator and then running AMPHI on the data. The corrections were observed to be small and were introduced via the b - factor in the CAL parameter file. The uncertainty in the absolute amplitude calibration is probably around the 10% level.

4.8 Model fitting

Model fitting is a technique which attempts to fit a model of the source to the observed visibility data. The model usually consists of one or more elliptical gaussian components described by six parameters: flux density, radius and position angle (P.A.) of the component from the centre of the field; the full-width half maximum (FWHM) of the major axis (M.A.), axial ratio (A.R.), and position angle (ϕ) of the major axis. All angles are measures in degrees (positive in the direction north through east) and all lengths are in milliarcseconds (mas).

Traditionally, model fitting has been used to produce simple source brightness distributions for short track observations where the (u - v) coverage is poor and hybrid mapping is unlikely to work. However, even if the coverage is relatively good and provided that the data set is not too large, model fitting can still be a useful exercise. In the case of 0957+561 A,B model fitting is appropriate since both images have simple structure and a simplified description of the source with few free parameters is desired.

Model fitting is a good method for deriving quantitative results (e.g. the relative positions and sizes of components). This is extremely important when comparing two images, in this case two gravitationally lensed images, of the same source.

The Caltech program MODELFIT measures the goodness of fit between the observed visibilities and the model visibilities by computing the well-known statistical function χ^2 that is defined as:

$$\chi^2 = \frac{1}{\eta} \sum_i \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{\sigma_E^2} \quad (4.17)$$

where O_i is the observed data point, E_i is the expected value from the model, σ_E^2 is the estimated variance of E_i (usually the error bar of O_i) and η is the number of degrees of freedom (equal to the number of independent data points — amplitudes and closure phases, minus the number of model parameters). The expected value of χ^2 is unity. MODELFIT tries to minimise the ‘agreement factor’, AF :

$$A = \sqrt{\chi^2} \quad (4.18)$$

In an iterative procedure the model parameters were obtained from a nonlinear, weighted least-squares solution, constrained by the correlated flux densities and the closure phase data. In general it is not possible to reach $\chi^2=1$. This is due to the model being simpler than the observed radio source structure and the presence of systematic errors in the data set caused by calibration errors.

ERRFIT can be used to obtain estimates of the formal error in each model parameter. In simple terms the program asks for a reasonable value of η , varies each parameter until χ^2 rises by $2/\eta$, and uses the values of E_i found in this process to estimate the formal error in each parameter.

4.9 Model fitting to the A and B images

The 13 minute data set was chosen as the input to the MODELFIT program because in its standard form it can only accept up to 200 visibilities. Contamination of the visibility amplitudes of the A image on the B image and vice versa was observed on the shortest baseline, Effelsberg – Westerbork. We attempted to correct for this by representing the contaminating image by an additional point source at the position of the other image in the initial source models. This was unsuccessful and data from the Effelsberg – Westerbork baseline were deleted from all data sets for model fitting.

Component	Flux (Jy)	Radius (mas)	P.A. (°)	M.A. (mas)	A.R.	ϕ (°)
Core (cpt 1)	0.024 ± 0.001	0.0	0.0	9 ± 3	$0.0003 \pm -$	44 ± 28
Jet (cpt 2)	0.027 ± 0.002	46.9 ± 0.5	21.4 ± 0.5	29 ± 3	$0.155 \pm -$	26 ± 4

Table 4.2: Model brightness distribution of image A, AF=1.495

Component	Flux (Jy)	Radius (mas)	P.A. (°)	M.A. (mas)	A.R.	ϕ (°)
Core (cpt 1)	0.019 ± 0.001	0.0	0.0	11 ± 3	$0.002 \pm -$	16 ± 16
Jet (cpt 2)	0.017 ± 0.003	57 ± 1	17.0 ± 0.6	34 ± 4	$0.0001 \pm -$	15 ± 5

Table 4.3: Model brightness distribution of image B, AF=1.616

Two-component Gaussian models were observed to fit the data well for both images. Tables 4.2 and 4.3 list the values of the parameters for these two elliptically shaped Gaussian brightness distributions that represent the A and B images. The relative positions of the model components in these tables (and in all others presented in this chapter) refer to epoch 1950.0. The models confirm the previous model-fitting results of Porcas *et al.* (1981), see tables 4.4 and 4.5.

The visibilities predicted by the model are shown by the solid lines through the data points in Appendix A. In some cases the program ERRFIT could not determine the uncertainty in some of the model parameters. This is usually an indication that the parameter is not well constrained by the data. Where this occurs in tables 4.2 and 4.3 the uncertainty has been replaced by a dash.

4.9.1 Results

It is clear (see Appendix A) that both the visibilities for the A and B images can be reasonably well represented by 2 component gaussian models, consisting of a barely resolved core and a thin elongated jet.

The values for the core-jet position angles and separations obtained from these models are nearly identical to those values by Porcas *et al.* (1981). The total flux of both images has apparently decreased from 61 mJy to 51 mJy (image A) and from 41 mJy to 36.6 mJy (image B). However, since the absolute flux calibration of both data sets is probably no better than $\approx 10\%$ this effect may arise from differences in calibration rather than source brightness variations.

The magnification ratio R, of the A and B images is an important parameter for lens modelling. Since it appears that the compact parts of 0957+561 A,B are probably

where ν is the frequency of observation, σ is the flux density error determined from ERRFIT (ignoring absolute calibration errors in both data sets) and S_{2292} , S_{1667} are the flux densities of the components at 2292 MHz ($\lambda 13$ cm) and at 1667 MHz ($\lambda 18$ cm). We obtain

$$\alpha_{A_{\text{jet}}} \approx -0.8 \pm 0.3$$

$$\alpha_{B_{\text{jet}}} \approx -0.5 \pm 0.6$$

$$\alpha_{A_{\text{core}}} \approx 0.2 \pm 0.1$$

$$\alpha_{B_{\text{core}}} \approx 0.3 \pm 0.2$$

4.10 Evidence for micro-lensing

We have seen that the magnification ratio appears to increase from 0.63 in the jets to 0.79 in the core. In addition, Vanderreist *et al.* (1989) finds the magnification ratio in the optical to be near unity. GOR88 have interpreted the difference between R_{core} and R_{jet} as changes in the brightness distribution of the core. An alternative

	Porcas <i>et al.</i>	GOR88	New data
$A_{\text{core}}/A_{\text{jet}}$	0.91	1.23	0.89
$B_{\text{core}}/B_{\text{jet}}$	1.41	1.46	1.12

Table 4.6: The flux ratio of core to jet for the A and B images

explanation proposed here is that the radio core and optical continuum of image B are being brightened by micro-lensing. This is quite plausible since one would suspect that the surface density of stars is larger for image B than for image A, and that B has therefore been brightened absolutely by micro-lensing while A is less influenced. The micro-lensing explanation is also in accord with the observation that the flux ratio of core to jet has been consistently greater in the B image than in the A image (see table 4.6)

4.11 Three gaussian component brightness distributions

The two component models fit the visibility data well. GOR88 require 4 gaussian components to fit their $\lambda 13$ cm VLBI ($\Delta\theta \approx 3.4$ mas) data completely.

Component	Flux (Jy)	Radius (mas)	P.A. (°)	M.A. (mas)	A.R.	ϕ (°)
Core (cpt 1)	0.029±0.001	0.0	0.0	3.5±1.5	0.5±0.1	-10±6
Jet (cpt 2)	0.032±0.001	46±1	21±1	38±3	0.35±0.04	27±3

Table 4.4: Model brightness distribution of image A, from Porcas *et al.* 1981.

Component	Flux (Jy)	Radius (mas)	P.A. (°)	M.A. (mas)	A.R.	ϕ (°)
Core (cpt 1)	0.024±0.001	0.0	0.0	2.5±2.7	0.5±0.2	-7±15
Jet (cpt 2)	0.017±0.001	56±2	17±1	37±6	0.36±0.1	28±3

Table 4.5: Model brightness distribution of image B, from Porcas *et al.* 1981.

affected by micro-lensing (Vanderreist *et al.* 1989), only comparison of extended parts can give an accurate value for R. This extended component cannot be too large however, otherwise the magnification might change across its surface. The VLBI jet of models 1 and 2 is therefore ideal for establishing a value for R. We obtain

$$R_{\text{jet}} = B_{\text{jet}}/A_{\text{jet}} = 0.63 \pm 0.12 \quad (4.19)$$

This is in excellent agreement with the result of GOR88, $R_{\text{jet}} = 0.64 \pm 0.03$. Note that since the A and B image data sets have been calibrated in exactly the same way this result is unaffected by any overall flux scale error. If we consider the unresolved cores we obtain a value for the magnification ratio:

$$R_{\text{core}} = B_{\text{core}}/A_{\text{core}} = 0.79 \pm 0.05 \quad (4.20)$$

Similarly GOR88 obtain a value $R_{\text{core}} = 0.82 \pm 0.02$.

If we are prepared to ignore absolute calibration offsets and resolution effects we can compare our data set with GOR88 to estimate the spectral index of the VLBI core and jet, for each image. We compare our flux density values of core and jet with the total (core + jet 1) and ('jet 2' + 'jet 3') flux densities as measured by GOR88. As expected the spectral indices of the core and jet of image A ($\alpha_{A\text{core}}$ and $\alpha_{A\text{jet}}$) are observed to be similar (within the uncertainties) to those measured for the B image. The spectral index (in the sense $S \propto \nu^\alpha$), was calculated for A and B and their uncertainty σ_α by

$$\alpha = \ln \left(\frac{S_{2292}}{S_{1667}} \right) / \ln \left(\frac{2292}{1667} \right) \quad (4.21)$$

$$\sigma_\alpha = \left[\left(\frac{\sigma_{2292}}{S_{2292}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{1667}}{S_{1667}} \right)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} / \ln \left(\frac{2292}{1667} \right) \quad (4.22)$$

It was decided to investigate whether our data were consistent with their models. We replaced the single gaussian component representing the jet structure (see table 4.3) of the B image with two gaussian components, placed close to the location of GORSS's jets 2 and 3. This was then used as a starting model for the MODELFIT program.

Component	Flux (Jy)	Radius (mas)	P.A. (°)	M.A. (mas)	A.R.	ϕ (°)
Core (cpt 1)	0.016±0.001	0.0	0.0	4.2± -	0.0041± -	32±-
Jet 2 (cpt 2)	0.007±0.002	61±2	18±2	10.8± -	0.0001± -	-10± -
Jet 3 (cpt 3)	0.013±0.004	48±11	17±3	68± 25	0.0000± -	15± 5

Table 4.7: Three component gaussian model brightness distribution of image B, AF=1.483

Component	Flux (Jy)	Radius (mas)	P.A. (°)	M.A. (mas)	A.R.	ϕ (°)
Core (cpt 1)	0.021±0.002	0.0	0.0	5.8± -	0.56± -	74.0±-
Jet 2 (cpt 2)	0.009±0.003	50±1	19±2	0.0± -	0.0001± -	-10± -
Jet 3 (cpt 3)	0.023±0.001	43±4	23±2	51± 13	0.12± -	26± 3

Table 4.8: Three component gaussian model brightness distribution of image A, AF=1.366

The final 3 component model shown in table 4.7 was found to fit the data better than before. For comparison the 'agreement factor' for the 3 component model was 1.483, compared to an 'agreement factor' of 1.616 for the 2 component model. Although improvements were made to the fit between the model amplitude and the observed amplitude most of the improvement was due to an improved fit to the closure phase. This may be expected as the closure phase is telling us about the relative position of the components.

To verify whether we were really sensitive to Jet 2 we used the final 3 component model of image B shown in table 4.7 as a starting model for the A image. The final 3 component model for the A image after model fitting is shown in table 4.8. Plots of both three component models for each of the A and B images are shown in figure 4.4. For comparison the 4 component models of GORSS are presented in tables 4.9 and 4.10.

It is clear from the model plots in figure 4.4 that the starting model for image A has been flipped over so that jet 2 is now on the opposite side of jet 3 in image B. Evidence that the parities of the A and B images are different was first presented by GORSS. Our model fitting results clearly support this view.

Component	Flux (Jy)	Radius (mas)	P.A. (°)	M.A. (mas)	A.R.	ϕ (°)
Core (cpt 1)	0.0207 ± 0.0003	0.0	0.0	1.29 ± 0.04	0	25 ± 1
Jet 1 (cpt 2)	0.0051 ± 0.0005	3.3 ± 0.3	27.3 ± 1	5.2 ± 0.6	0.1 ± 0.1	13 ± 2
Jet 2 (cpt 3)	0.009 ± 0.001	50.1 ± 0.3	20.0 ± 0.3	9 ± 1	0.44 ± 0.06	40 ± 5
Jet 3 (cpt 4)	0.012 ± 0.001	42.2 ± 2	22 ± 1	54 ± 7	0.10 ± 0.03	-27 ± 2

Table 4.9: Four component gaussian model brightness distribution of image A, from GOR88

Component	Flux (Jy)	Radius (mas)	P.A. (°)	M.A. (mas)	A.R.	ϕ (°)
Core (cpt 1)	0.0161 ± 0.0004	0.0	0.0	1.19 ± 0.05	0.37 ± 0.06	13 ± 2
Jet 1 (cpt 2)	0.0048 ± 0.0005	3.3 ± 0.4	12 ± 3	8 ± 1	0	19 ± 1
Jet 2 (cpt 3)	0.0053 ± 0.0005	60.3 ± 0.3	18 ± 1	10 ± 1	0.28 ± 0.04	6 ± 4
Jet 3 (cpt 4)	0.009 ± 0.001	50 ± 3	17 ± 1	66 ± 10	0.04 ± 0.01	17 ± 1

Table 4.10: Four component gaussian model brightness distribution of image B, from GOR88.

4.12 Mapping procedure

Hybrid mapping can reveal complex details of the source, particularly low brightness diffuse structure. Hybrid maps were made of both images using the iterative self-calibration procedure of (Cornwell & Wilkinson 1981). All the data processing was done either with the Caltech VLBI package or the Astronomical Image Processing System (AIPS, written at NRAO).

Biretta, Moore & Cohen (1986) have shown that by using reasonably accurate models of the source structure as starting models for the self-calibration procedure, improvements upon maps made with a point source assumption can be made. In addition, the convergence of maps made in this way is speeded up and the problems of spurious symmetrization (Linfield 1986) are reduced.

Hence, for each of the A and B images the simple 2-component gaussian models of the previous sections were used as starting models for self-calibration. The initial self-calibration was performed within the Caltech package. The routine AMPHI was used to self-calibrate the data. AMPHI was chosen rather than the AIPS routine ASCAL, as it is much easier to incorporate 2 - component gaussian models as the initial starting model for the self-calibration. The Effelsberg - Westerbork baseline was deleted from the B image data set but was retained in the A image data set, where the contamination problem was not so pronounced. Both data sets used a coherent

Figure 4.4: The surface brightness distributions for the gaussian models presented in tables 4.8 and 4.7. Image A is shown to the left and image B to the right. Contours (in percent) are drawn at 1,2,4,8,16,32, and 64 of the peak surface brightness for each image.

integration time of 120 s. The AIPS routine VBCIT was used to convert Caltech Merge data to AIPS format. After self-calibration the u - v data were sorted from time-baseline to x - y order for the FFT (Fast Fourier Transform), using UVSRT. The AIPS routine MX was used to FFT and CLEAN (Högbon 1974) the self-calibrated data. The CLEAN components were then used as the next components for the starting model of the next self-calibration. This was performed by ASCAL and then CLEANed in the usual way. The map was observed to converge after only a few cycles of this iterative loop. The maps were restored by a circular CLEAN beam with a FWHM of 15 mas.

Figure 4.5: Plot of the dirty beam with contours at 25, 49, 50, 51 and 75% level. The full width at half maximum is ≈ 15 mas

As can be seen from figure 4.5 this is the smallest beam one can employ without super-resolving. Trying to super-resolve with smaller beams appears to generate structure in the images which is spurious.

4.12.1 Image parities

The hybrid maps of the A and B images are shown in figures 4.6 and 4.7. Both maps show the basic 'core-jet' structure revealed by model fitting. Also there is little, if any, extended emission beyond a radius of about 100 mas. The dynamic range (measured as the ratio of the peak brightness to r.m.s. noise away from the map centre) is $\approx 170:1$ for the A image and $\approx 270:1$ for the B image. The hybrid maps of figures 4.6 and 4.7 support the model fitting result that the A and B images have opposite relative parities. The evidence for this comes from the appearance of the jets in each image. The jet in image A appears to curve to the left whereas the jet in image B curves to the right. Also the outside contours of the jet in the A image are flat on the left hand

side and curved on the right hand side. Similar structure is observed in the B image but on opposite sides.

Figure 4.6: A hybrid map of the A image made with a circular restoring beam of 15 mas (FWHM). The logarithmic contour levels are -0.35, 0.35, 0.70, 1.40, 2.80, 5.60, 11.20 mJy beam^{-1} . The peak flux is 22.07 mJy beam^{-1} .

Figure 4.7: A hybrid map of the B image made with a circular restoring beam of 15 mas (FWHM). The logarithmic contour levels are -0.35, 0.35, 0.70, 1.40, 2.80, 5.60, 11.20 mJy beam⁻¹. The peak flux is 17.94 mJy beam⁻¹.

4.12.2 Wide-field map of the B image

The presence of a compact component, G' , lying close to the optical position of the main lensing galaxy G1 has been reported by Gorenstein *et al.* (1983). They searched a region 0.2 arc sec North, 0.2 arc sec East, 0.2 arc sec West and 0.6 arc sec South of the VLA position for the Galaxy G1. The only significant signal was found 0.181 arc sec East and 1.029 arc sec North of the VLBI core of the B image. Much debate has centred on whether this is the radio core of G1 or the elusive third image predicted by theory.

We attempted to detect this source by making a wide-field map of the B image. Like most VLBI data sets the $u-v$ data points had a wide range of sensitivities. In particular, the longer baselines were particularly noisy as the telescope at Medicina had only an uncooled receiver. Thus the type of weighting to be employed in the mapping process had to be chosen with care.

Natural weighting (weighting based on sensitivity) reduces the noise in the map, but will cause the $(u-v)$ plane to be dominated by the stronger baselines. Uniform weighting recovers the $(u-v)$ plane well, reducing the sidelobe levels but resulting in the map noise being dominated by the weakest baselines. In our case we were interested in detecting a weak source far from the phase centre of the map.

It was therefore, decided that the best scheme for weighting the data in the mapping process would be to use natural weighting rather than the uniform weighting used in the previous hybrid maps. The data were self-calibrated and CLEAN'ed as before. All of the field was CLEANed, no CLEAN windows were set around any region of the image. The CLEAN components were used as the model for subsequent iterations. After a few iterative mapping cycles the CLEAN image as displayed by the AIPS TV routine TVL0D and TVFID showed an unresolved component lying close to the position of G' given by Gorenstein *et al.* (1983). The standard AIPS task IMFIT was used to fit a gaussian shaped component to G' and the core of the B image. G' was found to have a peak flux of ≈ 0.7 mJy/beam, well above the r.m.s. noise level of ≈ 60 μ Jy/beam. The position (relative to the core of B) and strength of the component was then used to produce a three component gaussian model for image B.

In the previous attempts at model fitting, the visibility data had been averaged up to 780 s. To investigate models in which the G' component was represented, the visibility data used a coherent integration time of 120 s. This was still large enough to produce a reasonable signal to noise, but small enough to ensure that the visibility

fringes were sampled often enough, to avoid smoothing. The Caltech MODELFIT program was modified² to accept up to 600 visibilities on each baseline.

The original 2 component model for B (see table 4.3) plus the IMFIT position and flux for G' were used as the starting model for the MODELFIT program. It was observed that the program changed the position of the third component only slightly (≈ 2 mas), placing it further eastwards of the original IMFIT position. Table 4.11 shows the 3 component model parameters which incorporate G'. The best fit was obtained with G' positioned 179.5 mas East and 1028.3 mas North of the core of B

Component	Flux (Jy)	Radius (mas)	P.A. ($^\circ$)	M.A. (mas)	A.R.	ϕ ($^\circ$)
Core (cpt 1)	0.020 ± 0.001	$0.0 \pm -$	$0.0 \pm -$	$9.5 \pm -$	$0.6 \pm -$	$17.7 \pm -$
Jet (cpt 2)	0.019 ± 0.005	56 ± 2	17 ± 2	38 ± 7	$0.189 \pm -$	14 ± 10
G'	0.001 ± 0.001	1044 ± 40	9.9 ± 2.2	$0.0000 \pm -$	$0.8 \pm -$	$0.0 \pm -$

Table 4.11: Model brightness distribution of image B and G'

The final three component model obtained was used to self-calibrate the original data with AMPHI and this was then transferred to AIPS as before. The data were then re-mapped. Again the map converged within a few mapping cycles. The final map is shown in figures 4.8 and 4.9. The main improvement to the original map is that the strength of the third component has increased from ≈ 0.7 mJy to 1 mJy. Measurements made of the r.m.s. noise in both maps were virtually the same.

The relative position of G' relative to the core of B was measured by IMFIT and MAXFIT. The AIPS task MAXFIT is less sophisticated than IMFIT. It attempts to fit a quadratic function to a specified 3×3 pixel map area in order to find the pixel location of the extremum. No error checking or goodness of fit analysis is made in MAXFIT. Measurements made by IMFIT and MAXFIT gave the following results:

AIPS Routine	Position of G' rel. to core B (mas)		Peak Intensity (mJy/beam)	Integrated Intensity (mJy)
	east	north		
IMFIT	179.0 ± 1.2	1026.2 ± 1.2	0.98 ± 0.02	1.07 ± 0.06
MAXFIT	178.5	1026.2	0.96	-

Table 4.12: Relative position of G' (with respect to B), peak and total flux.

A similar wide-field map of the A image is shown in figure 4.10. No evidence for radio emission ($> 300 \mu\text{Jy/beam}$) beyond ≈ 100 mas of the core was found.

²This makes the program run very slowly and does not work well if the input model lies far from a true minimum in the AF

Figure 4.8: Central portion of a wide-field hybrid map of the B image made with natural weighting and a circular restoring beam of 18 mas (FWHM). The contour levels are -0.20, 0.20, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9, 1, 2, 4, 18, 16 mJy beam⁻¹. The peak flux is 17.66 mJy beam⁻¹.

Figure 4.9: Wide field hybrid map of the B image made with natural weighting and a circular restoring beam of 18 mas (FWHM). The contour levels are -0.50, 0.50, 1, 2, 4, 8, 16 mJy beam⁻¹. The peak flux is 17.96 mJy beam⁻¹.

Figure 4.10: Wide-field hybrid map of the A image made with natural weighting and a circular restoring beam of 18 mas (FWHM). The contour levels are -0.50, 0.50, 1, 2, 4, 8, 16 mJy beam^{-1} . The peak flux is $23.19 \text{ mJy beam}^{-1}$.

4.13 The nature of G and G'

There can be little doubt that the compact component detected in the wide-field hybrid maps of the B image (figure 4.9) is the component G'. The 3 component gaussian model presented in table 4.11 and the results from the fitting routines IMFIT and MAXFIT suggest it is unresolved with a total flux of ≈ 1 mJy. As discussed in section 3.7 it is still unclear whether this is the third image or just the core of the lensing galaxy, G1. If this emission emanates wholly from the core of the main lensing galaxy then we can place a $300 \mu\text{Jy}$ (5σ) limit on the flux of the third image $B2/B1 < 0.8\%$. If on the other hand, the emission is entirely from the third image then $B2/B1 \approx 2.5\%$.

Roberts *et al.* (1985) noted from their VLA maps that G' lay slightly but significantly south and east of the radio source position measured for G. It is therefore useful to compare the EVN maps with the $\lambda 18$ cm MERLIN map shown in figure 3.5.

Using IMFIT and MAXFIT to measure the position of G with respect to B (this includes the VLBI core and jet for MERLIN and VLA images) from the MERLIN map gives the results shown in table 4.13. The uncertainties quoted were produced by the

AIPS Routine	Position of G rel. to B (mas)		Peak Intensity (mJy/beam)	Integrated Intensity (mJy)
	east	north		
IMFIT	148 ± 8	1093 ± 8	1.25 ± 0.03	1.6 ± 0.1
MAXFIT	148	1103	1.24	

Table 4.13: Relative position of G with respect to B, Peak and Total flux.

IMFIT program.

To check the accuracy of the errors determined in this way the relative separation of the A image with respect to the B image was determined using both routines. These were then compared with the the highly accurate VLBI observations (Gorenstein *et al.* 1984). IMFIT measured ($-1''.248 \pm 0''.008, 6''.044 \pm 0''.008$) and MAXFIT measured ($-1''.247, 6''.043$). These figures compare well with the more accurate VLBI results, ($-1''.25257, 6''.04663$). As suggested by the fitting routines it appears that we can measure differences in position to better than ± 10 mas in both the east-west and north-south directions.

4.13.1 The effect of image structure on the relative positions of G, G' and G1

Before plotting the positions of G, G' and G1 on the same figure we must consider the effects that the structure within the B image has on the measured relative positions. Since the restoring CLEAN beam in the MERLIN and VLA maps (≈ 350 mas) cannot resolve the core - jet structure that is observed in higher resolution VLBI maps, the position of the B image as measured by IMFIT and MAXFIT must refer to a position which lies at the centroid of the core and jet components.

From our $\lambda 18$ cm EVN map we can use the relative positions and fluxes of the core and jet components in the B image to estimate the positional offsets that should be applied to components measured with respect to the VLBI core of the B image e.g. G'. We calculate that such components must be shifted 26 mas south and 8 mas west if they are to be compared with the measured positions of G obtained from the MERLIN map. This offset must be regarded as a lower limit, since the MERLIN observations are much more sensitive to the extended emission which appears to lie between the VLBI jet and G.

For the same reasons it is difficult to directly compare the VLA position for G' with the MERLIN position. The $\lambda 6$ cm VLA observations made by Roberts *et al.* (1985) are less influenced by the steep spectrum VLBI jet and its extension. It is difficult to estimate how large an offset is required here but it is certainly smaller than that applied to G'. Unpublished $\lambda 6$ cm VLBI observations (P. Elosegui, private communication) show the jets to be barely detectable above the noise level, a factor of 5 weaker than the core of the B image. We have adopted the positional offset as the average of the two extremes originally suggested by Roberts *et al.* (1985). The VLA position for G has therefore been offset 6 mas west and 21 mas south.

We note that if we apply a similar correction to the relative separation of the A and B images due to the differences in the core-jet separations and position angles we find that we underestimate the separation by 3 mas (N-S) and by 1 mas (E-W). Applying this correction to the IMFIT and MAXFIT measurements brings us into closer agreement with the VLBI results of Gorenstein *et al.* (1984).

Figure 4.11: A subsection of the $\lambda 18$ cm MERLIN map of 0957+561, showing the B image and the G component. Plotted on top of this figure is the position of G as measured by MERLIN and the VLA, the position of G' as measured by EVN and the optical position for G1. 1 pixel = 100 mas. All positions are shown relative to the MERLIN position for the B image as discussed in the text.

In figure 4.11 the MERLIN position for G, the VLA position for G and the EVN position for G' are all plotted with respect to the position for B as measured in the MERLIN map. Assuming that the optical core of B and the VLBI radio core are coincident we have plotted the position of G1 with respect to the position of G'. The MERLIN and EVN positions were obtained from the average of the IMFIT and MAXFIT results. All four components are plotted on top of the B and G components of the MERLIN $\lambda 18$ cm map. Error bars of 10 mas on each side are plotted for the radio sources.

The error box plotted around G1 comes from the positional uncertainty quoted by Stockton (1980). The relative position of A with respect to B that Stockton used to determine his plate scale is slightly different from the more recent VLBI results of Gorenstein *et al.* (1984). Applying this correction to Stockton's original analysis results in a small correctional offset. The original position ($0''.19, 1''.0$) for G1 is displaced 5 mas to the west and 1 mas to the south resulting in a corrected position (0.185,0.999). It is this position for G1 that is plotted in figure 4.11

4.13.2 Explaining the positional offset between G and G'

It appears from figure 4.11 that there is a real positional offset between the measured positions of G and G' (G lies ≈ 72 mas north and 30 mas west of G'). If we ignore the possible variability of G and G' (the MERLIN observations were made in February 1989 compared with the EVN observations in February 1987) more than half of the flux of G must come from G'. The total flux of G as measured from the MERLIN maps (by AIPS task IMEAN) is 1.8 mJy while the total flux of G' from the EVN map is ≈ 1 mJy. It is difficult to understand how the positional offset can arise if G and G' are one and the same source. If we identify G' as the radio core of G1 then the obvious conclusion must be that there is structure within the radio component G. This is probably made up of a compact core G' and some extended 'jet like' emission. If the core and the extended emission are of roughly equal flux (as suggested by the MERLIN and EVN maps) then the components should be separated by ≈ 150 mas. The MERLIN map appears to show an extension of G towards the north west, although admittedly this is seen at the lowest believable contour level.

An alternative explanation is that G' is the third image and that the extended emission is associated with the galaxy G1. This is a proposition which must be taken seriously. It is an attractive one since the separation between G' and G is of the same

order and lies in the same direction as that predicted by lens models for the separation of G1 from the third image. The major stumbling block for this interpretation is that the measured position for G1 is coincident with G' within the observational uncertainties. However, the position of G1 was obtained from a complicated subtraction procedure and it is not inconceivable that it is badly in error.

4.14 Conclusions

The high resolution EVN hybrid maps confirm the presence of core-jet structure in each of the A and B images. Differences in the form of the jet support the view that the images have opposite parities. Model fitting to the visibilities lends further weight to this view. The parameters derived from model fitting can be used to constrain lens models for 0957+561. A magnification ratio free from the effects of micro-lensing has been determined from the ratio of the jet fluxes. We interpret the increase in the magnification ratio, R , from 0.63 in the jet to 0.79 in the core, as being due to the radio core of the B image being brightened by micro-lensing.

It has been demonstrated that, with care, searches for compact components in this field can be conducted by making wide-field hybrid maps of each image. This method is superior to the brute force searches in fringe rate and delay space as employed by Gorenstein *et al.* (1983). The construction of wide-field maps allows a much larger area to be searched for a relatively small investment of processing time. This technique will play an important part in the success of future observations of the double quasar.

A wide-field map of the A image has been made for the first time. This shows no emission larger than 300μ Jy beyond a radius of 100 mas. A similar wide-field map of the B image shows a third unresolved component lying close to the optical position for G1 with a total flux ≈ 1.0 mJy. Its position measured with respect to the EVN core of B allows us to identify it as G', the compact VLB component discovered by Gorenstein *et al.* (1983). A comparison between this wide-field map and a recent $\lambda 18$ cm MERLIN map imply that there is a real positional offset between G' and G of ≈ 78 mas. If we identify G' as the radio core of G1 then this offset must be the result of structure within G.

Chapter 5

Spectroscopy of the lensing cluster

The observational data, however, is still not adequate to define the lens model uniquely, and what is particularly needed is the position of the effective cluster-centre. — Narasimha, Subramanian & Chitre (1984)

5.1 Introduction

Soon after the discovery of the main lensing galaxy, G1, YGKOW obtained deep CCD frames of the field surrounding 0957+561. These revealed that G1 was just one of 180 objects in the field (see section 3.4). The richness of the field suggested that G1 was the brightest member of a cluster of galaxies situated at $z \approx 0.36$. In addition, the large 6'' separation between the A and B images could only be explained in terms of lensing by G1 *and* the rest of the cluster.

As a result YGKOW attempted to determine a luminosity-weighted centre for the cluster but, without spectroscopic identification for all but three objects in the field, the position they derived was very sensitive to contamination by background and foreground objects. Indeed, early modelling work by Narasimha, Subramanian & Chitre (1984), Higgs (1984) and Greenfield, Roberts & Burke (1985) found it impossible to reconcile the details of the VLBI core-jet structure observed in both images (Porcas *et al.* 1981) with lens models in which the cluster centre was positioned in the region YGKOW suggested (approximately 20 arc sec west of the A and B images). Hence, the importance of obtaining redshifts for the brightest galaxies in the field became clear.

In this chapter we present the results of a spectroscopic survey of the field using the technique of multi-slit spectroscopy. The programme was designed to determine redshifts for the brightest galaxies in the field. As well as providing information about the structure of the lens and its centre, it was also realised that such a programme might also be able to determine the velocity dispersion of the cluster.

Figure 5.1: An example of a mask (approximately to scale) and the recorded spectra from the CCD chip. The B image of 0957+561 was used as the set up object for this slit. The associated slits can be seen near the centre of the mask, lying on the same vertical line. The intense bands running horizontally across the chip (the spatial dimension) are due to sky lines. The faint vertical lines running along the dispersive axis are spectra of the sources of interest. Two objects can be seen in the second slit from the left. Note that for each spectrum, the correspondence between wavelength and row number is different due to the slits being staggered.

5.2 Data acquisition

The spectra presented in this thesis were obtained on the nights of 2 – 5 March 1987 and 12 – 14 March 1988. The observations were made with the 4 m telescope at Kitt Peak National Observatory (KPNO) with the Cryogenic Camera in multi-aperture mode.

The camera consists of an evacuated f/1 classical Schmidt design with a thinned Texas Instruments 800×800 pixel CCD at the focus. However, the optical system only illuminates the central 350×800 pixel area of the chip. The spectral range is typically 4800–7800Å with a resolution of 15Å (4Å per pixel). The chip has a read out noise of 8–10 electrons r.m.s. The dispersive element consisted of a transmission grating replicated on the hypotenuse exit face of a right angled prism. This design is known as a ‘grism’.

In multi-aperture mode the normal slit of the spectrograph is replaced by an aperture plate assembly. The multi-slit aperture masks are made from high contrast photographic film. The film is opaque except for 6–12 slits that are staggered to correspond to the positions of the target objects in the field. There is a slight loss in throughput by the film (DeViny 1985), but this is believed to be small ($\approx 10\%$). An example of a mask and the recorded spectra are shown in figure 5.1.

The object selection, positions of the slits, their lengths and the appropriate sky position angle of the mask were designed by hand. The mask design was then fabricated by the KPNO Photo Lab and the Instrument support group. These final films were then precisely cut on a special cutter for exact alignment on registration pins in the aperture plate holder used in the telescope. In 1987, 0957+561 B was used as a set up object, sitting permanently in one of the slits. The encoder was then relied upon to give the correct position angle for the aperture plate.

Analysis of the 1987 data provided evidence that errors in the aperture plate rotation angle had resulted in objects at the edge of the mask sitting off centre in the slit. In 1988, a different method was chosen to set the position angle. All the masks were designed for use at position angle 90° or 180°. At least two widely separated set up slits (length $\approx 5''$) were produced for each mask. To ensure that the position angle was correct for each mask the set up source was tracked between the two slits in declination or right ascension. The separation of the set up slits was limited by the field of view of the TV acquisition system. Fine adjustments to the position angle were made using a small d.c. rotator motor. Set up sources included 0957+561 A,B plus a bright star also

in the field. The 15.4 magnitude star was too bright to remain in the set-up slit for the full exposure time and was used only for the initial alignment. Once the position angle was checked a small offset of 3" was introduced to remove the star from the set-up slit. Accurate offsetting was achieved by using the auto-guider.

The slit width was 2.0"–2.5". The slit length varied from slit to slit but was always larger than the smallest recommended value of 12". Typically values much larger than this were used particularly with the fainter objects so that good sky background subtraction could be achieved. Space existed for approximately 8–10 galaxies in each mask.

Exposures using integration times longer than one hour are quantum noise limited. Hence, the total integration time was typically ≈ 3600 seconds. As a result several exposures of the same mask were made and later added together either by adding the frames or the extracted spectra. As well as taking exposures of the target field, calibration frames were also taken before and after data were recorded. These calibration frames included:

- dark frames for bias subtraction
- quartz-comparison frames and dome-flats for flatfielding purposes
- blank sky frames used to determine the slit function
- reference spectra provided by a He-Ne-Ar lamp

The mask was left in place for all the above calibration frames. To check that the exposure had worked properly each CCD frame was displayed on the Grinell imaging device.

5.3 Data reduction procedure

Data reduction was performed using the starlink packages Figaro and DIPSO.

5.3.1 Cleaning the image

The first step was to remove cosmic ray events from the CCD frames. This was done in an interactive mode since for many of the frames the S/N ratio was low. This was a laborious task but it was the only way of ensuring that the job was done properly. Automatic removal routines such as CLEAN in Figaro can result in strong emission lines being mistaken for cosmic ray hits.

5.3.2 Averaging the data

Many exposures were taken using the same mask. By collapsing each data frame along the dispersive axis it was possible to compare each frame, looking for positional shifts. In most cases these shifts were negligible and the data frames were simply added together and averaged. In some cases shifts along the spatial axis were identified. These data frames were then reduced individually. They were added to the corresponding averaged frames after the spectra had been extracted. In some cases where a number of individual extracted spectra were added together, these were given a weight, proportional to the $(S/N)^2$.

5.3.3 Bias subtraction

To remove the signal that is registered by the CCD in the absence of light, the bias level, a series of zero-exposure images were taken. These were then added together and an average taken. The bias could also be determined from the un-exposed edge of the chip (columns 481-512). This bias was subtracted from all images.

5.3.4 Flatfielding

Quartz-comparison frames were used for flatfielding purposes. The flatfield is designed to compensate for pixel-to-pixel variations across the CCD chip. Each quartz frame was checked for shifts in feature positions to see if there was any obvious motion of the instrument over the time during which a particular mask had been used. These shifts were found to be negligible in nearly all cases. The best signal-to-noise flatfield was therefore obtained by adding the quartz frames together and taking an average. To correct for the large scale structure in the quartz spectra a low order polynomial was fitted along each of the columns (parallel to the dispersive axis) of

Figure 5.2: Changes in the slit profile due to loss of focus at the extreme ends of the chip. The profiles were produced by collapsing the CCD frame along the dispersive axis. Four profiles are shown: rows 601-800 (red), rows 401-600, rows 201-400 and rows 1-200 (blue). Note that the source signal appears as a small blip on top of the sky background. Plots such as these are used to determine those columns to be used for extracting the source and sky spectra.

the averaged quartz frame. This produced a smoothed image which was then divided into the un-smoothed frame. The resulting normalised image was then used to correct for the pixel-to-pixel response across the chip: the flatfield was divided into all the remaining images.

5.3.5 Slit function correction

The sky flats were used to correct for the throughput differences across the length of the slit. The central region of each sky flat (rows 300–500) was collapsed along the dispersive direction. The resulting 1-D profile is a fair representation of the slit function. This single function was then expanded along the dispersive axis to become a 2-D image. A suitable constant was chosen to normalise the resultant image. This slit function frame was then divided into each of the data frames.

As shown in figure 5.2 the slit profile appears to change along the dispersive axis, possibly due to variable focussing effects. Unfortunately, there was no simple way within Figaro to obtain a slit function which would take into account the differences in the profiles along the dispersive axis. Hence, a compromise was made by only collapsing the in-focus, central area of the chip (rows 300–500).

5.3.6 Sky subtraction

The extracted sky background spectra are obtained by collapsing along the spatial axis those columns on either side of the object spectrum and taking the average. Similarly the object spectra is extracted in exactly the same way. The extracted sky background spectra is then subtracted from the object spectra.

The central 300–500 columns of each data frame was collapsed along the dispersive axis. The profile created (see figure 5.2) was then used to decide which spatial columns should be included as the sky background extracted spectra and which should be included as object extracted spectra. The sky regions were easily defined. Each region was chosen so that it lay far enough away from the edge of the slit (to avoid edge effects) and far enough away from the source so that it was un-contaminated by the object spectra. In general, sky background spectra could be extracted on either side of the source. In some cases however, the object was observed to lie slightly off centre in the slit. In extreme cases the sky could only be extracted from one side of the slit. Since we had already allowed for larger slit lengths than strictly necessary this was not a major problem. An example of an extracted sky spectrum is shown in figure 5.3.

The spatial columns chosen to be used to extract the object spectrum were harder to define. Due to seeing effects and the natural extension of the galaxy the source spectrum was detected in several spatial columns, each at a different signal level. Unfortunately, it was not possible to weight the individual columns in Figaro. The criterion for choosing which column should be included and which should not was accomplished by hand. If all the columns which contain some source signal are used the extracted spectrum can be unnecessarily noisy (Horne 1986). If the object spatial profile can be approximated to be gaussian, it appeared that the best results were produced by excluding those columns in which the signal was less than $\approx 50\%$ of the FWHM power point.

Figure 5.3: An example of an extracted sky spectrum.

5.3.7 Wavelength calibration

The He-Ne-Ar comparison arc frames were added together after it was determined that no shifts had occurred between frames along the dispersive direction. The comparison spectra were then extracted from the averaged frame.

The Figaro ARC routine was used to determine the wavelength to channel number relationship. This required wavelength identification of known arc lines. Once a line has been identified, ARC fits a gaussian to the line profile to determine its centre. When more than one line has been identified ARC begins to calculate the fit to the

identified lines. Once all the lines are identified ARC computes the goodness of fit. The r.m.s. for the current fit is displayed along with statistical information on how individual identifications have affected the final r.m.s. Any obvious mis-identifications can be deleted and a fresh attempt made to obtain a fit.

Once a satisfactory fit was obtained, the calibration was applied to the appropriate sky-subtracted spectrum. A final check on the accuracy of the wavelength scale was made by measuring the positions of sky lines on the sky background extracted spectrum. All calibrations were found to be accurate for our purposes. No attempt was made to flux calibrate the spectra since only spectral features were of interest.

5.3.8 Redshift determination

Gaussian profiles were fitted to the strongest emission or absorption line features to determine redshifts for the objects. The STARLINK spectral analysis package, DIPSO and its associated ELF (Emission Line Fitting) routines were used to determine centre positions and line widths. Although ELF is nominally intended for emission line fitting it is entirely happy with absorption lines, which it treats as emission lines with negative flux.

It was first necessary to subtract the continuum from each spectrum. This is important as each spectral line contains a component due to the optical continuum of the source. To subtract the continuum a polynomial was fitted to those parts of the spectrum free from absorption or emission lines. This polynomial fit was then subtracted from the spectrum. A subsection of the spectrum which included the feature under investigation was chosen. Routine ELFOPT was used to obtain a gaussian fit to the feature. The program required an initial guess for the line centre and its width before employing an iterative procedure to generate an optimum fit to the line. Figure 5.4 shows the main steps in the fitting procedure.

Figure 5.4: The procedure for fitting a gaussian to the [OIII] (5007Å) feature found in object 20. A polynomial is fitted to the continuum of the spectrum. This polynomial fit is then subtracted from the spectrum as shown top right. Bottom right shows the subsection of the spectrum which includes the feature of interest. At bottom right is shown the gaussian fit to the feature.

5.4 Nomenclature

YGKOW were able to compile a list of objects in the field, classifying them as stars, galaxies or quasars, depending on their photometric profile. Each was given a number which we will refer to as Young's Number (e.g. Y10). These numbers are arranged in order of increasing right ascension. For the purposes of this thesis we introduce another number which we will refer to as the rank number. These are applied to those objects classified as galaxies by YGKOW but excluding the brightest galaxy G1. The rank number increases with decreasing brightness. Hence, R1 refers to the brightest galaxy in the field excluding G1 (i.e. G2 is YGKOW's notation).

Rank No.	Y's No.	z	Features identified
R1	Y55	0.3587 ± 0.0004	[OII](em),K,H
R2	Y7	0.2391 ± 0.0002	[OII](em),H,H β ,[OIII](em)
R3	Y54	0.357 ± 0.001	[OII](em),K,H
R4	Y19	0.5030 ± 0.0004	K,H,G
R5	Y122	0.353 ± 0.001	K,H,G
R6	Y94	$0.353 \pm 0.002^*$	K,H,[OII](em)
R7	Y20	$0.5052 \pm 0.004^*$	K,H,G
R8	Y134	0.3548 ± 0.0004	K,H,G
R10	Y174	0.3545 ± 0.0006	G
R11	Y135	0.6047 ± 0.0006	K,H,[OII](em)
R12	Y144	$0.3523 \pm 0.0003^*$	[OII](em),K,H β (em),[OIII](em)
R13	Y97	$0.3535 \pm 0.0006^*$	H,K,G
R15	Y167	—	Stellar spectrum
R16	Y118	0.359 ± 0.002	H,K,
R17	Y57	—	Stellar spectrum
R18	Y157	$0.2400 \pm 0.0001^*$	H β (em),[OIII](em)
R19	Y116	0.353 ± 0.001	H,G
R20	Y74	$0.3525 \pm 0.0002^*$	[OII](em),H β (em),[OIII](em)
R21	Y61	0.3074 ± 0.0009	[OII](em),K,H,[OIII](5007)(em)
R22	Y13	—	Stellar spectrum
R23	Y2	0.5024 ± 0.0009	H
R33	Y40	0.503 ± 0.001	H,G

Table 5.1: Redshift determinations. [OII] refers to the $\lambda 3727\text{\AA}$ and [OIII] refers to $\lambda 5007\text{\AA}$ and $\lambda 4959\text{\AA}$ lines. For galaxy R21 only the [OIII] $\lambda 5007\text{\AA}$ line was used for the fit. An asterix in column 3 is used to note that the standard deviation is quoted as the formal error.

5.5 Results

We obtained redshift determinations for a total of twenty two objects. The redshifts of only two objects (R9 and R14) out of the first 23 brightest galaxies remain undetermined. Of the brightest twenty three objects, eleven have redshifts at $\bar{z} \approx 0.355$, four have redshifts at $\bar{z} \approx 0.503$, two have redshifts at $\bar{z} \approx 0.240$, one at $z \approx 0.605$, one at $z \approx 0.307$ and three are identified as field stars. The spectra obtained are displayed in Appendix B.

Table 5.1 summarises the results. The lines identified in bold type are those used to give the redshift values. Emission lines are indicated by the label (em). All other lines are absorption features. In some cases the redshifts were determined from more than one line and an average taken. In these cases both lines are shown in bold type and the standard deviation is quoted as the formal error. In all other cases, the formal error is determined from the uncertainty in the measured centre wavelength of the line.

5.6 A second cluster at $z \approx 0.503$?

Perhaps our most important result is the discovery of four galaxies (R4, R7, R23, R33) with similar redshifts, $\bar{z} \approx 0.503$. The tight positional grouping of these objects (R7, R23 and R33 all lie within $31''$ of R4) suggest that they may be the brightest members of a second cluster of galaxies close to the line of sight. Figure 5.5 shows the positions of the brightest 35 objects in the field (originally classified by YGKOW as galaxies and excluding the two quasar images - QSOA and QSOB). Without further spectroscopy in this region it is impossible to say whether the four galaxies are the brightest members of a cluster similar in size to that observed at $\bar{z} \approx 0.355$ or whether they are just an isolated group of galaxies. R2 and R18 also have similar redshifts, ≈ 0.24 but they are separated by $159''$.

5.7 Luminosity-weighted centre

Following YGKOW, we assume the mass of each galaxy to be proportional to the flux of the galaxy. Each galaxy at $z \approx 0.36$ was assigned a weight value, L_i given by the ratio of the fluxes, F_i :

$$L_i = F_i / F_1 \quad (5.1)$$

where F_1 is the flux of the brightest galaxy (R1) and i is the rank of the i^{th} galaxy at $z \approx 0.36$. We then calculated $\bar{C}_L(0.36)$, the cluster's luminosity-weighted centre of mass, by computing

$$\bar{C}_L(0.36) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n L_i \bar{C}_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n L_i} \quad (5.2)$$

where $\bar{C}_i(0.36)$ is the vector position, in arc seconds (w.r.t. 0957+561 B) of the galaxy with rank number= i .

Figure 5.5: Positions of the thirty five brightest objects in the field (originally classified by YGKOW as galaxies) relative to the B image. The galaxies with $z \approx 0.355$ are shown as filled triangles, the open triangles those whose redshift remains unknown (objects 9 and 14 are labelled), galaxies at $z \approx 0.503$ are displayed as filled circles, galaxies at $z \approx 0.240$ are unfilled circles, and the galaxies at $z \approx 0.605$ and $z \approx 0.307$ are represented by empty squares. The field stars are displayed as five pointed stars. Note how close the galaxies at $z \approx 0.503$ (filled circles) lie relative to each other.

Out of the twenty three brightest galaxies in the field only two remain unidentified — R9 and R14. Excluding R9 and R14 we obtain the result:

$$\bar{C}_L(0.36) = (-3.5'', 1.2'') \quad (5.3)$$

Including R9 and R14 we obtain the result:

$$\vec{C}_L(0.36) = (-4.7'', 4.5'') \quad (5.4)$$

These results compare with that determined by YGKOW:

$$\vec{C}_L(0.36) = (-21.9'', 3.4'') \quad (5.5)$$

Without redshift confirmation it is probably prudent to assume that R9 and R14 are cluster members. Their positions on the sky are shown in figure 5.5. Spectra of poor quality were obtained for both these objects but no conclusions could be drawn from them. Interestingly, R9 lies close to the four galaxies at $z=0.50$. R14 is close to the edge of the field but it cannot be concluded to be a non-cluster member; object 10, for example, is also close to the edge of the field.

If the four objects at $z=0.50$ are the brightest four of a cluster we obtain a cluster centre, $\vec{C}_L(0.50)$:

$$\vec{C}_L(0.50) = (-79.4'', 46.5'') \quad (5.6)$$

5.8 Velocity dispersion of the cluster at $z \approx 0.355$

To obtain accurate velocity measurements for the galaxies at $z \approx 0.36$ the spectra were cross-correlated with a reference spectrum. We chose two of the highest signal to noise spectra - R1 and R3 as our primary reference spectra. They both exhibited [OII] $\lambda 3727\text{\AA}$ in emission and the H and K features in absorption. It was important that the reference galaxies should exhibit well defined H and K absorption lines as these were the most common features in the lower signal to noise spectra. The use of two reference galaxies allowed us to check on the consistency of the final results.

5.8.1 Cross-correlation of the spectra

The DIPSO routine XCORR was used to cross-correlate the spectra. Having subtracted the continuum from the spectra each was cross-correlated in two narrow wavelength regions roughly corresponding to the [OII] emission line (4950-5150 $\text{\AA}$) and the 4000 $\text{\AA}$ H and K break (5250-5450 $\text{\AA}$). The cross-correlation regions were made long enough to avoid any edge effects but not so long that spurious features could be mistaken as real spectral features. Each cross-correlation function was assessed and

the best one chosen to determine the wavelength shift. In those cases where cross-correlation functions of similar quality existed in both the [OII] and H and K wavelength ranges, an average shift was determined. Cross-correlation functions were also produced for selected objects in the $H\beta$, [OIII] and G band wavelength regions. Cross-correlation of non-reference cluster members, allowed us to check the consistency of our results. For example, the G band feature in reference object R1 was very poor. In contrast R10 exhibited a clear G band. We therefore cross-correlated those spectra with well defined G bands with R10 (see bottom of table 5.2). Emission line objects R12 and R20 were cross-correlated across the [OIII] and $H\beta$ regions.

Rank No*R2	x-c region(s) (Å)	x-c λ shift (Å)	ΔV (km s ⁻¹)	ΔV (km s ⁻¹)
R3*R1	4950-5150 (g)	-10±2	-590±120	-520±100
	5250-5450 (g)	-8±2	-450±110	—
R5*R1	5250-5450 (f)	-24±4	-1340±220	—
R6*R1	4950-5150 (f),	-18±4	-1070±240	-1210±200
	5250-5450 (f)	-24±4	-1350±225	—
R8*R1	5250-5450 (g)	-20±4	-1120	-1120±220
R10*R1	4950-5150 (g)	-16±4	-950±240	—
R12*R1	4950-5150 (g)	-28±2	-1660±118	-1500±230
	5250-5450 (g)	-24±3	-1341±170	—
R13*R1	5250-5450 (f-g)	-17±4	-950±220	—
R16*R1	5250-5450 (p)	-2±6	-110±330	—
R19*R1	5250-5450 (f-g)	-25±4	-1400±220	—
R20*R1	4950-5150 (g)	-27±2	-1610±120	—
R20*R12	4959-5150 (g)	2±2	90±90	—
	6560-6790 (g)	2±2	—	—
	6680-6800 (g)	2±2	—	—
R20*R10	4950-5150 (g)	-12±3	710±180	—
R10*R12	4950-5150 (g)	14±3	830±240	—
R5*R10	5650 5860 (f)	-6±3	310±160	—
R8*R10	5650 5860 (p)	1±4	52±210	—
R13*R10	5650 5860 (f)	6±3	310±160	—
R19*R10	5650 5860 (p)	-10±4	520±200	—

Table 5.2: Cross-correlation velocity shifts at $z=0.355$ using galaxy R1 as the reference template. The bottom half of the table shows the results of non-reference galaxy cross-correlations. These latter results are consistent (within the measurements errors) with those presented in the top half of the table.

5.8.2 Results

Tables 5.2 and 5.3 show the main cross-correlation results for the cluster at $z \approx 0.355$ using templates R1 and R3 respectively. The lower half of table 5.2 also contains

results of non-reference galaxy cross-correlation. In table 5.4 the cross-correlation results of objects R7, R23 and R33 are shown, object R4 having being used as the reference galaxy. In the same table, the results of cross-correlating R18 and R2 are also displayed.

In all tables, column 1 identifies the cross-correlated spectra. Column 2 gives the wavelength region over which the cross-correlation (x-c) took place and the quality of the corresponding cross-correlation function (g:good, f:fair, p:poor). For comparison figure 5.6 shows three cross-correlation functions of good, fair and poor quality. In columns 3 and 4 the shift in wavelength and velocity are given. In column 5 the average shift (if applicable) is displayed and the standard deviation is listed and used in place of the formal error. All formal errors shown in the tables were derived from an estimate of the uncertainty in the peak of the cross-correlation function.

The results from both the reference and non-reference galaxies are all consistent within the observational uncertainties. The line-of-sight velocity dispersion of the cluster at $z \approx 0.355$ derived from reference galaxies R1 and R3 respectively are

$$\sigma_r = 545 \text{ km s}^{-1} \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_r = 551 \text{ km s}^{-1}$$

It is encouraging to note that both references give similar results, although this should not be taken to be indicative of the associated errors.

Rank No* <i>R3</i>	x-c region(s) ($\text{\AA}$)	x-c λ shift ($\text{\AA}$)	ΔV (km s^{-1})	ΔV (km s^{-1})
R1* <i>R3</i>	4950-5150 (g)	10 ± 2	590 ± 120	520 ± 100
	5250-5450 (g)	8 ± 2	450 ± 110	—
R5* <i>R3</i>	5250-5450 (f)	-11 ± 4	-620 ± 220	—
R6* <i>R3</i>	5250-5450 (f)	-18 ± 3	-1090 ± 170	—
R8* <i>R3</i>	5250-5450 (g)	-14 ± 4	-800 ± 230	—
R10* <i>R3</i>	5250-5450 (f)	-12 ± 4	-670 ± 220	—
R12* <i>R3</i>	4950-5150 (f)	-16 ± 4	-950 ± 240	—
R13* <i>R3</i>	5650-5860 (f)	-10 ± 3	-520 ± 160	—
R16* <i>R3</i>	5250-5450 (p)	6 ± 6	340 ± 340	380 ± 60
	5650-5860 (f)	8 ± 3	420 ± 160	—
R19* <i>R3</i>	5250-5450 (f)	-14 ± 6	-790 ± 220	—
R20* <i>R3</i>	4950-5150 (f)	-16 ± 3	-950 ± 180	—

Table 5.3: Cross-correlated velocity shifts at $z=0.355$ using galaxy R3 as the reference template

Figure 5.6: Three cross-correlation functions of good, fair and poor quality (top to bottom). The last function was not used to derive the velocity shift.

Since only four galaxies were identified at $z=0.50$ it was not possible to give a reliable value for the velocity dispersion of the cluster. The results (table 5.4) from the three cross-correlation functions which were obtained do show the velocity differences to be small. The two objects (R2 and R18) at $z \approx 0.24$ show a very small velocity difference (also table 5.4).

Rank No* <i>R</i> 4	x-c region(s) (Å)	x-c $\Delta\lambda$ (Å)	ΔV (km s ⁻¹)	$\Delta \bar{V}$ (km s ⁻¹)
R7* <i>R</i> 4	5910-6150 (g)	7±3,	350±150	—
R23* <i>R</i> 4	5910-6150 (p)	-1±4	-50±200	-70±130 (30)
	6400-6600 (f-g)	2±4	-90±180	
R33* <i>R</i> 4	5910-6150 (p-f)	3±4	150±200	—
R18* <i>R</i> 2	6000-6240 (g)	4±2	200±100	—

Table 5.4: Cross-correlated velocity shifts at $z=0.503$ using *R*4 as the reference template

5.9 Conclusions

A total of 22 redshifts have been determined for objects in the field. Twenty of these are for the brightest 23 objects, leaving only *R*9 and *R*14 unaccounted for. We have determined a luminosity-weighted centre for the cluster at $z \approx 0.355$, using 11 of the 13 brightest member galaxies. The new centre lies much closer to *G*1 and the images, than the position first suggested by YGKOW. We have also determined a tentative value for the cluster's line-of-sight velocity dispersion $\sigma_r \approx 548$ km s⁻¹ (the average of the *R*1 and *R*3 dispersions). These results provide important new constraints which can be incorporated into lens mass models of 0957+561 A,B.

The discovery of four galaxies with the same redshift ($z \approx 0.503$) lying close to each other on the sky suggests that a second cluster of galaxies may be involved in the lensing. It is unclear whether the four galaxies are the brightest members of a cluster similar in size to that observed at $z \approx 0.355$ or whether they are just an isolated group of galaxies. Using the four galaxies identified at $z \approx 0.503$ a luminosity-weighted centre has been computed.

The presence of two lenses at different redshifts (referred to as a 'double lens') can considerably complicate the imaging. In particular, how might the presence of a second cluster effect our ability to constrain the mass of the main lensing galaxy *G*1 ? In the

next chapter we describe the results of modelling programs that have been written to address this and related problems.

Chapter 6

Lens Models

To search for and find images in a gravitational lens model is not a trivial task. — Schramm & Kayser (1987)

6.1 Objectives

The long promised cosmological applications of gravitational lenses (Canizares 1987) require a good understanding of the lensed system, particularly the mass distribution of the lens. The fundamental aim of lens modelling is therefore to deduce this mass distribution from the distorted images of the undeflected source. Clearly any information about the structure of the lens itself is useful in constraining the lens mass distribution. Successful lens models of 0957+561 must be capable of reproducing the main features of the small scale core-jet structure seen in the EVN observations and the large scale structure (singly imaged north-easterly and south-westerly jets) seen in the MERLIN and VLA images of the source.

The evidence for a second cluster of galaxies (lying close to the line of sight, $z \approx 0.50$) as discussed in chapter 5 has led to the investigation of both single and double plane lens models for 0957+561. Since one of the original aims of this project has been to determine the mass of the main lensing galaxy, G1, it is important to study how the imaging may be effected by the size and mass of this second cluster.

The models presented in this chapter have been obtained from the combined application of programs LENCAL and BILDEN, both of which were written by the author of this thesis. We begin therefore with a general account of lens modelling and the construction of these programs.

6.2 The Gravitational lens mapping

As discussed in section 2.2 the mapping between the image plane and the source plane is a surjective mapping. In other words, one particular source point can be mapped on to several different image points but one particular image point can never be mapped

on to more than one source point. If for the moment we assume that we have a complete knowledge of the lens mass distribution then the situation can be summarised by figure 6.1

Figure 6.1: The mapping between the image plane and the source plane is a surjective mapping. In general, no explicit formulation of the multi-valued inverse lens equation exists.

The surjective nature of the lens equation (see equation 2.4) suggests two possible strategies for modelling gravitationally lensed systems. One can either:

- choose a model for the deflector and a source position. Find the image positions by numerical inversion of the lens equation. Compare the images found with those seen on the sky. If the observed and predicted images are identical within the measurement errors then a good lens model has been found; *or*
- choose a model for the deflector and trace the light rays from the images back through the deflector towards the source plane. If the resulting source positions coincide then a good model has been found.

Up until recently these two methods have been used in isolation. For example, the work of Higgs (1984) was based solely on the second method. This method is more attractive than the first for two main reasons. Firstly, it does not require knowledge

6.4 Program LENCAL

LENCAL is written in standard FORTRAN77 and uses the SDF method to determine the position, shape and relative brightness of the images of a lens system, given the redshift and mass distributions of the lenses and the position of the original undeflected source. The mass distributions are represented by the King model approximation (see section 2.3.1) introduced by YGKOW. Each lens is specified by its angular position on the sky, position angle of the major axis (north through east), velocity dispersion, ellipticity and core radius. LENCAL allows the use of two lens planes with up to 20 individual lens masses in each plane.

An example of a contour plot produced by the program is shown in figure 6.2.

In addition to LENCAL programs FIDDLE and EXFUN have also been written. FIDDLE takes the 'source subtracted SDF array' (produced by LENCAL before it terminates) and allows different source positions and sizes to be tried. The final SDF array (source included) is written out to a file which can be read into AIPS. This allows the use of the image processing functions to be found within AIPS. For example figure 6.3 is the grey scale version of figure 6.2 produced by the AIPS task GREYS. By using the AIPS tv routines TVPSE and TVFID it is in fact possible to see the effects of different source sizes in real time. Program EXFUN reads in any number of SDF arrays (source included) and adds them together. In this way it is possible to see the images that might be produced from a multi-component source. The brightness ratios are no longer comparable however.

It is worth commenting here on some of the limitations of the SDF method. For example, the grid density sets an upper limit on the weakest images that can be found. If the grid box size is larger than the image size then the detection of the image becomes a matter of chance. This problem can usually be solved by increasing the size of the source (i.e. increasing the contour values) until the image is larger than the grid box size. However, this will not work if the brighter images overrun the field before the weak image has been detected. If there is still a suspicion that an image has not yet been found it is worth while increasing the grid density or setting a smaller image search window around the point of interest. A combination of both techniques means no images need be missed.

Figure 6.3: A Grey scale version of the contour plot shown in figure 6.2.

6.5 Program BILDEN

Program BILDEN uses the method employed by Higgs (1984) of ray tracing backwards from the image plane to the source plane. For each image position seen on the sky there is a corresponding source position:

$$\bar{\theta}_S = \bar{\theta}_I - \bar{\alpha}(\bar{\theta}_I) \frac{D_{AS}}{D_{OS}} \quad (6.3)$$

Hence, for any particular lens system associated image points must be mapped back onto the same source point (see figure 6.1). In practice, the lens mass is not well

known and many different lens models must be tried until one is found for which the differences between the source positions (as predicted from equation 6.3) is smaller than some limiting value (usually the observational uncertainty in the image difference positions).

Models can be compared by computing the square of the differences, GFIT, between the predicted source positions ($\bar{\theta}_{S1}$, $\bar{\theta}_{S2}$ etc):

$$\text{GFIT} = |\bar{\theta}_{S1} - \bar{\theta}_{S2}|^2 \quad (6.4)$$

In the case of the double quasar BILDEN extends the concept of the goodness of fit to include the differences between the source positions corresponding to the multiply imaged VLBI jets and the differences between observed and predicted image amplification ratios. A penalty value is also added to those models which predict third images with amplification ratios (relative to the B image) greater than that deduced from observational limits. Program BILDEN computes the sum of squares for each lens model:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{GFIT14} = & \left(|\bar{\theta}_{\text{Core A}} - \bar{\theta}_{\text{Core B}}|^2 \right) \frac{1}{W_C^2} \\ & + \left(\ln \left(\frac{R_{\text{obs}}}{R_{\text{model}}} \right) \right)^2 \frac{1}{W_R^2} \\ & + \left(|\bar{\theta}_{\text{Jet A}} - \bar{\theta}_{\text{Jet B}}|^2 \right) \frac{1}{W_J^2} + P \end{aligned} \quad (6.5)$$

where core A and core B refer to the undeflected source position of the VLBI core determined from the A and B image VLBI core positions, similarly Jet A and Jet B refer to the undeflected source position of the VLBI jets determined from the EVN A and B image jet positions (see section 4.9). R_{obs} and R_{model} are the observed and model predicted image flux ratio, (B/A).

Each of the terms in equation 6.5 is given a weight W which is roughly proportional to the square of the uncertainty in each of the difference quantities. ($W_R \approx 0.05$, W_C and $W_J \approx 0.001$ arcsecond). P is the penalty value (1000) added to those models with third images brighter than 1.6% of B. If the flux ratio is less than 1.6% no penalty is added to the sum. Since the contribution to GFIT14 is < 1 for a term in which the undeflected objects coincide within the 1σ confidence level, a good model may be considered to be one for which $\text{GFIT} \sim 3$.

In this way the image observables can be used to constrain the lens mass distribution of the lens. Any knowledge about the structure of the lens itself can be used to reduce the number of models that must be tried. Fortunately, in the case of the double quasar, detailed observations have allowed a range of lens model parameters to be determined. Nevertheless, the lens model 'parameter space' that must be searched is enormous.

6.5.1 How BILDEN works

BILDEN works through each of the four terms in equation 6.5 summing the GFIT contributions at each stage. If at any stage GFIT is greater than a maximum acceptable value (FITCUT) specified by the user, then BILDEN will reject the present model and start on the next untried model. This simple cut-off approach reduces the run time of BILDEN by a considerable amount. The technique does not appear to have been used by Harding (1982) or Higgs (1984). Their models did not compute the goodness of fit until all of the image characteristics had been determined.

BILDEN calculates the amplification of each image by moving the source position to three points which describe a triangular region centred on the point of interest. A corresponding triangular region is mapped onto the image plane. The amplification is just the ratio of the two triangular areas.

Within BILDEN resides a routine which is virtually identical to LENCAL. This is used to find the dim third image. The routine is restricted to a 1.25" square field centred on the position of the main lensing galaxy.

6.6 Hardware

Both BILDEN and LENCAL were compiled and ran on the Jodrell Bank mini-supercomputer, the Alliant FX/8. A UNIX¹ based machine, the Alliant was one of the first affordable vector/parallel processing mini-supercomputers to appear in the latter half of the 1980's.

At present the Alliant contains four computational elements (CE's), giving it a theoretical capacity of 47 Mflops. To maximise efficiency, each processing job is divided between the CE's. If the CE's are not busy then they will resume primary responsibility for most operating system processes. However, if any large computer-intensive jobs are

¹More specifically the operating system is CONCENTRIX Alliant's own version of Berkeley UNIX but with special extensions for parallel processing.

running, three interactive processors (IP's) can be used to communicate with the disks, execute user jobs (such as those that do not require the computational performance of the CE's, e.g. editing) and generally manage the operating system. This division of labour allows the CE's to concentrate on the 'number crunching' while the IP's ensure that the system remains responsive to the normal user.

The Alliant's FX/FORTRAN compiler attempts to detect the potential for parallel processing in standard FORTRAN code (such as repetitive calculations or loops). This allows the code to be optimised with the minimum of user intervention or programmer time. For any sizeable program (BILDEN is 3000 lines long) there will be sections of the code which the compiler will not be able to optimise. In such cases the area is highlighted during compilation with informational messages which may be used as a starting point from which to restructure the code. In any event programs will still run whether they are fully optimised or not.

Even although some of the BILDEN and LENCAL code remains unoptimised they run ≈ 5 times faster on the Alliant than on the STARLINK MicroVAX 3400. BILDEN is able to search through approximately 10^7 models in 6 hours and LENCAL (using a 200×200 grid) can find and display images in ≈ 70 seconds.

6.7 The bend angle array

While working on early versions of LENCAL and BILDEN it soon became clear that the majority of computer processing time was devoted to calculating the bend angle (see equation 2.22) associated with each of the image points. This has to be computed for each of the grid points ($\approx 4 \times 10^4$ points) specified in LENCAL and for each of the images in the 10^7 models that BILDEN might search through in a typical run.

To overcome this difficulty it was decided to pre-calculate the bend angle outside of the main programs. Program DEFGAL was written to calculate the vector bending angle, $\vec{\alpha}$, of a photon passing an elliptical lens mass. By gridding the lens mass, $\vec{\alpha}$ was calculated at many points within the lens. When all the points were determined within a user defined area (referred to as the 'array extent'), the array of bend angles thus produced was written out to a disk file in the form of an unformatted array. Due to the assumed elliptical symmetry of the lens mass distribution we need only determine $\vec{\alpha}$ in one quadrant. For the other three quadrants only a change of sign in either α_x or α_y is required. This can be determined in the main program subroutines.

Since in general the photon impact position w.r.t. to the centre of the lens will not lie exactly on a pre-determined array point, an interpolation procedure was devised to compute the bend angle for any specific impact position.

It does not seem unreasonable to use these gridding and interpolation techniques when we consider that the King model is itself only an approximation to the true mass distribution of the galaxy. In practice, the method does not appear to produce any unwanted artifacts in the imaging process (very close double or triple images) that one might expect from a distorted distribution.

The bend angle array produced by DEFGAL corresponds to an elliptical lens with a velocity dispersion of 300 km s^{-1} . The units of position are the dimensionless units of structural length discussed in section 2.3.1. If the lens mass specified in LENCAL or BILDEN has a velocity dispersion σ_v then to obtain α from the array we just scale the deflection by $(\sigma_v/300)^2$.

Save for the ellipticity of the lens, all other parameters such as the position angle and structural length can take on all reasonable values without specialised bend angle arrays being recalculated. However, if one lens mass has a structural length of 0.5 kpc (a galaxy say) and another 50 kpc (perhaps a cluster) then it is sensible to use two different bend angle arrays, and grid each appropriately. Unfortunately, each array can only be used for the particular ellipticity determined originally in DEFGAL. This restricts the parameter space that can be searched using any particular bend angle array but the gain in cpu time using this method is sufficiently large to outweigh this disadvantage.

For BILDEN the extent of the array does not need to be particularly large. The reason for this is that we know where the images are on the sky so that for any particular lens we need only calculate the bend angles for a very small region in the sky. Even taking into account the effects of varying lens positions and structural lengths it is possible to use arrays in which the array grid is extremely dense.

6.8 Combined application of LENCAL and BILDEN

One of the first models used to test program LENCAL was a solution obtained by Higgs (1984) using Young's interpolation formula. The lens model parameters are presented in table 6.1. The subsequent SDF plot is shown in figure 6.4. The undeflected source position is positioned $(-2.24'', -9.68'')$ w.r.t. the B image.

A plot of the subsequent SDF array is shown in figure 6.4. The model appears to reproduce the observed image locations of the A and B images in 0957+561. If we now allow the image search window to increase in size new images are detected to the south of the A and B images. A contour plot is shown in Figure 6.5. It can be seen that the additional images are of the same order of brightness as the A and B images. To ensure that the extra images were not due to the sparse 200×200 SDF image grid LENCAL was re-run with a 500×500 grid. The resulting SDF plot confirms the presence of the extra images and shows virtually the same features as those seen in the 200×200 plot. In fact the plot shown in figure 6.5 was made from the 500×500 SDF grid. A further check was made on this result by determining the source position associated with each of the images. Each of the images was found to have the same source position within the expected uncertainties (~ 1 grid spacing in the SDF array).

How can we explain such images lying this far from the centre of the lens? As noted by Young *et al.* (1980) it is possible for the cluster itself to produce highly amplified images at large distances from the centre if the velocity dispersion is high enough. It seems likely that this is the explanation for the extra images produced by Higgs' model.

This result highlights a fatal flaw within modelling programs which follow the method of BILDEN alone. Using this method it is possible for a lens model which produces more images than are actually seen on the sky to satisfy all the known image properties and thus to be regarded as a good solution. For this reason it is essential that lens models produced using this ray tracing method must be tested both in the source plane *and* the image plane, using a combination of programs such as BILDEN and LENCAL. This philosophy has been employed in the modelling described in the remainder of this chapter.

Lens model parameter	G1	Cluster
Position (w.r.t.) B (")	(0.190,1.000)	(-5.46,-9.57)
Axis ratio (b/a)	0.782	0.430
Position angle ($^{\circ}$)	55.9	85.2
Radial velocity dispersion (km s^{-1})	265.8	1154
Structural length (kpc)	0.352	63

Table 6.1: Model parameters for a solution produced by Higgs (1984).

Figure 6.4: A plot of the SDF array produced from the lens model of Higgs (1984). The model appears at first sight to reproduce the A and B image positions. Note the weak third image which lies close to the centre of the main lensing galaxy.

Figure 6.5: A plot of the SDF array with a larger search window. The extra images can be seen to the south of the A and B images.

6.9 Lens model constraints

The observational properties of the cD galaxy G1 and the associated cluster are shown in table 6.2. The uncertainties quoted, were taken from the corresponding references which are identified by superscripts. As noted by Higgs (1984) the errors appear to be fairly optimistic for some parameters. In some cases (e.g. the cluster centre) it is extremely difficult to assign meaningful errors. Rather than interpreting the parameters presented in table 6.2 as hard and fast limits, they should be regarded as no more than a guide to the parameter space that can be searched.

Constraint	G1	Cluster
Redshift	0.36 ± 0.01^a	0.355^b
Position (w.r.t.) B (")	$(0.190 \pm 0.030, 1.000 \pm 0.030)^c$	$(-4.7, 4.5)^d$
Axial ratio (b/a)	0.87 ± 0.01^a	0.54^a
Position angle ($^\circ$)	53 ± 5^a	90^a
Radial velocity dispersion (km s^{-1})	—	548^b
Structural length (kpc)	0.445 ± 0.167^c	93^a

^a YGKOW

^b This thesis (section 5.5)

^c Stockton (1980)

^d This thesis (section 5.7).

Table 6.2: Properties of G1 and the cluster at $z \approx 0.355$

Image redshift	1.4136^c
VLBI core image separations (A-B) (1950.0)	$(-1.25251 \pm 0.00006, 6.04662 \pm 0.00004)^f$
EVN core-jet separation for image A	$(17.1 \pm 0.5, 43.7 \pm 0.2)^g$
EVN core-jet separation for image B	$(16.7 \pm 1.0, 54.5 \pm 0.3)^g$
Image magnification ratio (B1/A)	0.635 ± 0.007^h
Upper limit on flux ratio (B2/B1) ⁱ	0.016^j

^c Weymann *et al.* (1979)

^f Gorenstein *et al.* (1984)

^g This thesis (section 4.9.1)

^h Average value determined from results presented in this thesis (see g) and GOR88

ⁱ B1 refers to the observed B image and B2 the undetected third image

^j Based on the 5σ upper limit of 0.3 mJy for any undetected source in the field (flux of B = 19 mJy) searched by Gorenstein *et al.* (1983).

Table 6.3: Observed properties of the images.

A similar table 6.3 shows the observed properties of the images which are used to

constrain models for the mass distribution of 0957+561 produced by BILDEN. Placing an upper limit on the brightness ratio of the third image to the B image (B_2/B_1) is dependent on whether one believes G' to be the core of the lensing galaxy G_1 or the third image. If we take the 'worst case' and identify the emission solely with G_1 then from the EVN map $B_2/B_1 < 0.009$. However, since it is possible that G' is the third image then it was decided to use the upper limit originally used by Higgs (1984), i.e. $B_2/B_1 < 0.016$.

Early in the modelling phase of this project it was decided to take advantage of the work done by other authors. This resulted in the adoption of the double ellipsoid model for the galaxy and cluster at $z \approx 0.355$. Since the use of the bend angle array required an ellipticity to be fixed for both the galaxy and the cluster it was decided to choose the values found in Higgs' best solution using Young's interpolation formula, $b/a = 0.782$ for G_1 and $b/a = 0.43$ for the cluster.

Constraint	G_1	Cluster
Redshift	0.355	0.355
Position (w.r.t.) B (")	(0.190,1.000)	(0 $\pm$ 10,0 $\pm$ 10)
Axial ratio (b/a)	0.782	0.43
Position angle (°)	53 $\pm$ 5	90 $\pm$ 30
Radial velocity dispersion (km s ⁻¹)	250 $\pm$ 150	750 $\pm$ 450
Structural length (kpc)	0.445 $\pm$ 0.167	63 $\pm$ 30

Table 6.4: Lens model parameters from which the parameter space to be searched for the single plane lens models were based.

6.10 Early failures and changes to BILDEN

Initially we attempted to search for single and double plane lens models at the same time. However, for this to work with BILDEN it was necessary for the second cluster at $z \approx 0.50$ to be given a velocity dispersion of 0 km s⁻¹ if single plane models were to be considered. This is rather an inefficient method as it means that BILDEN treats the problem as a full scale double plane case for which the lens in the second plane has zero mass. It therefore calls on all the subroutines that are associated with double plane models.

This procedure was implemented on the first major run of BILDEN. Bench tests

suggested that BILDEN would take approximately 48 hours to run through the parameter space specified in the first script file². A batch job was submitted on the evening of Friday the 24th of November 1989. Having set the batch job running the progress of BILDEN was not checked until the following morning. Much to the author's despair it was not found to be running! Further, a listing of the solution file (which was empty) suggested that the program had in fact run no longer than two hours. Clearly not only had the speed of BILDEN been underestimated but so too had the number of models that would need to be searched before even rough solutions could be found. An extended file was hurriedly submitted. This job ran for 2 days and 4 hours and again produced no good solutions.

In its early form the FITCUT parameter (discussed earlier in section 6.5.1) was built into the program at compile time. From the beginning it was unclear what was likely to be a reasonable value. After the first unfortunate attempts, several smaller tests of BILDEN were run during the night until some experience was gained with the behaviour of the program. It was at this stage that BILDEN was modified to allow FITCUT values to be specified as an input parameter.

6.10.1 Modelling strategy

It was obvious from the early test runs of BILDEN that searching for both double and single lens models at the same time was stretching the size of the parameter space beyond reasonable limits. Hence it was decided to graduate to the more complex double plane models only after successful solutions had been found for the basic single plane case.

A modelling strategy also began to evolve. This strategy involved searching four sections of the parameter space divided by the ranges of cluster centre position. This position was constrained to lie within a 20 arcsecond box centred on B. It was divided by the four quadrants defined by the x and y axis passing through the origin (B). Within each quadrant 200 different positions were searched. Early results from this four pronged attack seemed to indicate that the lowest values of GFIT14 were largely to be found for models in which the cluster centre and the source position were both located above the x-axis i.e. to the north of image B. From this point onwards only models for which the cluster centre was above the x-axis were tested. In addition

²For this first run other Alliant users had been persuaded/bribed to execute only small tasks (the Alliant is almost exclusively used for AIPS processing) leaving the bulk of the cpu time available to BILDEN during the weekend

the structural length of the cluster which had initially been allowed to vary from 60 to 120 kpc was fixed at 63 kpc. As better models were found the parameter space was reduced still further by keeping the structural length of G1 constant. The search procedure developed in the following way:

- Solutions for which GFIT14 was less than FITCUT were written to the solution file
- The best solution was studied by LENCAL. In particular any model predicting more than three images was discarded
- BILDEN was then run on a subset of the original parameter space centred on the best solution found in the original solution file.
- good models were tested for the parity of the A and B images and the single imaging of the north-easterly and south-westerly radio jets associated with the A image.
- the process was continued until GFIT14 either converged or became smaller than 3.

6.11 Single plane lens models

In the following section we present two good solutions produced by BILDEN and LENCAL. These will be referred to as models 1 and 2. They are presented in tables 6.5 and 6.6 respectively. Each model was obtained independently through the individual application of the procedure described above. The goodness of fit (GFIT14) is less than 3 for model 1 and less than 4 for model 2. We compare aspects of these models with the observational evidence and attempt to predict from them the properties of the third image and the mass of the galaxy G1.

Perhaps the most striking thing about these models is that the one dimensional velocity dispersion of the cluster at $z \approx 0.355$ is smaller in all cases than that obtained by Higgs (1984) (1154 km s^{-1}) and Narasimha, Subramanian & Chitre (1984) (990 km s^{-1}) in their previous double ellipsoid models. Even so it is larger than the measured radial velocity dispersion presented in Chapter 5. Despite persistent efforts, no models could be found for which the velocity dispersion was much less than 800 km s^{-1} . However

as pointed out by Young *et al.* (1980) the observed velocity dispersion will be considerably less than that obtained in models if the cluster is appreciably flattened. This discrepancy between the observed velocity dispersion and the model velocity dispersion is therefore not unexpected.

Lens model Parameters	G1	Cluster
Position (w.r.t.) B (")	(0.190,1.000)	(-5.840,6.100)
Axial ratio (b/a)	0.782	0.43
Position angle (°)	50.913	70.80
Radial velocity dispersion (km s^{-1})	274.3	885.6
Structural length (kpc)	0.4	68

Image/source characteristics		
Undelected core position and jet separation	(-2.5669,5.7913)	(0.0139,0.0247)
Core position and jet separation of 3 rd image	(0.1850,0.8920)	(-0.0007,-0.0007)
Amplification (B1/A) and (B2/B1)	0.6333	0.0003

Table 6.5: Model 1 - a good single plane lens solution, GFIT14=0.4335

Lens model Parameters	G1	Cluster
Position (w.r.t.) B (")	(0.190,1.000)	(-2.961,3.022)
Axial ratio (b/a)	0.782	0.43
Position angle (°)	50.913	70.10
Radial velocity dispersion (km s^{-1})	309.3	786
Structural length (kpc)	0.36	68

Image/source characteristics		
Undelected core position and jet separation	(-0.9861,3.4483)	(0.0116,0.0314)
Core position and jet separation of 3 rd image	(0.1834,0.8928)	(-0.0035,-0.0031)
Amplification (B1/A) and (B2/B1)	0.6332	0.0081

Table 6.6: Model 2, GFIT14=3.7927

Although the structural length of G1 has to be nearer the lower end of the range suggested by Stockton (1980), it is larger than the model values required by Higgs (1984) and Narasimha, Subramanian & Chitre (1984) to maintain a faint third image (0.352 kpc and 0.333 kpc respectively). For model 1 the B2/B1 brightness ratio is extremely small ($< 0.03\%$).

6.11.1 Large scale radio structure

The reproduction of the singly imaged north-easterly and south-westerly radio jets associated with the A image and seen in VLA and MERLIN maps (see section 3.6.2) is shown for model 1 in figure 6.6. This was constructed by measuring the positions of the main features in the jets and ray-tracing backwards towards the source plane to find their undeflected positions. A combination of programs FIDFUN and EXFUN were used to produce the final image from an ensemble of *circular* source positions. Figure 6.7 shows how 0957+561 would look if it was not gravitationally lensed. The

Figure 6.6: The reproduction of the singly imaged north-easterly and south-westerly jets by model 1.

effect of lensing on the original source is quite dramatic. One can see that the core and the associated jet structure is being noticeably amplified. In the source plane the alignment between the undeflected north-easterly and south westerly is nearly straight, compared to the curved jets we see in the image plane. As noted by Greenfield, Roberts & Burke (1985) although the jets need not be straight, those in the luminosity class of 0957+561 tend to be so.

Figure 6.7: How the source predicted by model 1 would appear if one could 'turn off' the lens and see the undeflected source. Note that the radio components of the source have been crudely approximated by circles.

Although most of the north-easterly jet lies outside the caustic that divides the source plane into areas of single and triple imaging a small portion of the jet lying closest to the quasar core does appear to be multiply imaged. The coarse SDF plots

presented here show how the second and third images of the stub of the jet join together to form a bridge of emission between the B1 and B2 images.

This structure is consistent with the high resolution MERLIN map shown previously in section 4.13. Since the multiple imaging of the stub of the north-easterly jet was not a modelling constraint it is pleasing to note that the models presented here should predict its existence. The single imaging of the jets save for the stub of the north-easterly jet is repeated in the other models presented in this chapter. This gives us some degree of confidence in the models.

6.11.2 Properties of the third image

From the two models presented here, we see that the predicted position of the third image is similar for each model — lying approximately 110 mas due south of G1. The core-jet separation for this image varies from < 1 mas in model 1 to ~ 5 mas in model 2. The B2/B1 flux ratio is smaller in model 1 (0.03%) than in model 2 (0.8%). If we identify the compact component G' seen in the EVN wide field hybrid map with the core of the lensing galaxy G1, then one might possibly detect the third image predicted by model 2 but one would not detect that predicted by model 1. Even in the case of model 1 the flux of the third image is unlikely to be much greater than $300 \mu\text{Jy}$, just short of the level at which we are confident of being able to detect real features.

6.12 The effect of a second cluster on the imaging

Following the discovery of four galaxies at $z \approx 0.503$, all lying within $60''$ of each other on the sky (section 5.6), it was clear that some attempt must be made to establish what effect a second cluster (besides the one at $z \approx 0.355$) would have on the imaging of 0957+561. In particular, how might a second cluster affect our ability to provide useful estimates of the mass of G1.

One can obtain a very rough estimate of this effect by taking a good single lens plane model and adding the second cluster in the form of a simple spherically symmetric King model. By increasing the cluster's velocity dispersion in stages it is possible to see how the images evolve. Various velocity dispersions were tried (see table 6.7) and the effects on the images are shown in Figure 6.8.

Figure 6.8: The effect of introducing a second cluster at $z=0.503$ while keeping the other lens parameters constant. At top left the images produced for a velocity dispersion of 100 km s^{-1} , top right 200 km s^{-1} , bottom left 225 km s^{-1} and bottom right 250 km/s .

It can be seen that the system does not begin to change visibly until the velocity dispersion of the second cluster is $\approx 100 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. For a velocity dispersion of $\approx 200 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ the deviation from the original image is more noticeable. A slight increase of the velocity dispersion to 225 km s^{-1} and then 250 km s^{-1} sees the system change from a recognisable double quasar dog leg configuration, to one more reminiscent of the giant optical arcs discussed earlier in section 1.3.1.

Constraint	Cluster at $z \approx 0.503$
Redshift	0.503 ± 0.001^a
Position (w.r.t.) B (")	$(-79.4, 46.5)^a$
Axial ratio (b/a)	1
Radial velocity dispersion (km s^{-1})	0, 100, 200, 225, 250
Structural length (kpc)	50

^a This thesis (section 5.5)

Table 6.7: Lens model parameters for the cluster at $z \approx 0.503$

Of course this exercise is of only very limited value since none of the model or source parameters are allowed to vary in order to maintain the double quasar configuration. However, it does highlight the fact that relatively small changes in the lens model can result in very different image configurations. This is particularly true for systems like 0957+561 where the source lies close to a caustic.

A fairer test is to allow all the parameters to vary in an attempt to restore the image configuration to its original form.

6.13 Double plane lens models

Models 3 and 4 presented below are based upon model 1 discussed in section 6.11. The last parameter space file from which model 1 was obtained was used as the basis from which good double plane models were to be found. The intention was to examine how massive the second cluster could be made before good solutions could not be recovered. This gives us an indication as to when the second cluster switches from playing a fairly passive role to one in which its effect must be taken into account.

The position, position angle and ellipticity of the second cluster was identical to that used in the previous section (see table 6.7). The structural length was fixed at 68 kpc (the same as the cluster at $z \approx 0.355$) and the velocity dispersion was allowed to

take the values 25, 50, 75, 100, 150, 200, 250 and 300 km s⁻¹. Tables 6.8 and 6.9 show the only two solutions (models 3 and 4) to be obtained from the search. Predictably

Lens model Parameters	G1	Cl $z \approx 0.36$	Cl $z \approx 0.50$
Position (w.r.t.) B (")	(0.190,1.000)	(-5.840,6.100)	(-79.4,46.5)
Axial ratio (b/a)	0.782	0.430	1
Position angle (°)	50.92	70.8	-
Radial velocity dispersion (km s ⁻¹)	274.2	885.8	25
Structural length (kpc)	0.4	68	68

Image/source characteristics		
Undelected core position and jet separation	(-2.5767,5.7979)	(0.014,0.0247)
Core position and jet separation of 3 rd image	(0.1847,0.8918)	(-0.0004,-0.0004)
Amplification (B1/A) and (B2/B1)	0.6328	0.0003

Table 6.8: A double plane lens model, GFIT14=0.8311

Lens model Parameters	G1	Cl $z \approx 0.36$	Cl $z \approx 0.50$
Position (w.r.t.) B (")	(0.190,1.000)	(-5.840,6.100)	(-79.4,46.5)
Axial ratio (b/a)	0.782	0.430	1
Position angle (°)	50.92	70.8	-
Radial velocity dispersion (km s ⁻¹)	274.4	885.6	75
Structural length (kpc)	0.4	68	68

Image/source characteristics		
Undelected core position and jet separation	(-2.6438,5.8421)	(0.014,0.0247)
Core position and jet separation of 3 rd image	(0.1847,0.8918)	(-0.0004,-0.0004)
Amplification (B1/A) and (B2/B1)	0.6304	0.0003

Table 6.9: A double plane lens model, GFIT14=1.709

their velocity dispersions are at the lower end of the range. The models themselves are virtually identical except for the undeflected source positions which are slightly different from model 1. For velocity dispersions greater than 75 km s⁻¹ no solutions were found. Strangely no further solutions were found even when the parameter space was relaxed still further. It appears that for a cluster of structural length ~ 68 kpc this marks the point at which the second cluster begins to play an important role in the imaging.

To investigate double plane lens models further it was decided to investigate those models for which the second cluster took on values which might be representative of a fairly large cluster of galaxies at $z = 0.503$. We therefore chose the structural length to be 50 kpc and a range of velocity dispersions 160, 400 and 800 km s⁻¹. The other

parameters were not changed. The structural lengths of the galaxy and the cluster at $z = 0.355$ were fixed at 0.4 kpc and 68 kpc. However, the remaining parameters were allowed to take on all reasonable values although the cluster centre at $z = 0.355$ was constrained to lie within a small area (based on the luminosity weighted centre determined in section 5.7) ranging from $-3.5''$ to $-4.7''$ in x and $1.2''$ and $4.5''$ in y .

A double plane solution (model 5) is shown in table 6.10. The mass distribution located at $z \approx 0.355$ is little different from the single plane solutions presented earlier. For model 5 the presence of the second cluster at $z \approx 0.503$ appears to have slightly reduced the surface density required in the first plane. It is of course dangerous to make any general conclusions from this model alone, but such an effect might not be unexpected for double plane models.

Image/source characteristics			
Undelected core position and jet separation	(-3.7814,5.3035)	(0.0134,0.023)	
Core position and jet separation of 3 rd image	(0.1817,0.888)	(-0.0006,-0.0018)	
Amplification (B1/A) and (B2/B1)	0.6346	0.0043	

Lens model parameters			
	G1	C1 ($z \approx 0.36$)	C1 ($z \approx 0.50$)
Position (w.r.t.) B ($''$)	(0.190,1.000)	(-3.913,3.899)	(-79.4,46.5)
Axial ratio (b/a)	0.782	0.430	1
Position angle ($^\circ$)	54.1	70.7	-
Radial velocity dispersion (km s^{-1})	269.7	850.3	400
Structural length (kpc)	0.4	68	50

Table 6.10: Model 5, GFIT14=1.9935

6.14 The lens mass distribution

The original aim of this project was to determine the mass distribution of the main lensing galaxy G1. The models that have been discussed in sections 6.11 and 6.13 have been used to estimate the mass of G1 and the central density of the cluster. Since the imaging is only sensitive to the mass that lies within the impact position of image A we have determined the mass of G1 out to image A. Determining the total mass of the galaxy requires a dangerous extrapolation for which the result becomes heavily model dependent. This is because most of the mass lies outside the impact parameter defined by the A image. These notes of caution apply doubly to the cluster. It is prudent to quote only its central density. The mass of G1 out to image A and the central density

of the cluster at $z \approx 0.355$ have been determined for models 1,2 and 5 (the results for models 3 and 4 are identical to model 1). The figures are shown in table 6.11.

YGKOW estimate the central luminosity density of the cluster at $z \approx 0.355$ to be $\tau \sim 26.5/\text{arcsec}^2$ which corresponds to a B band luminosity of $\sim 1.6 \times 10^8 L_{\odot}$ (Greenfield, Roberts & Burke 1985). By comparison the surface mass density of the cluster in model 1 is $5.5 \times 10^{10} M_{\odot}/\text{arcsec}^2$. This suggests $M/L \sim 340$. Similarly for G1 YGKOW obtained an integrated magnitude $r \sim 18.5$, which corresponds to a B band luminosity of $2.5 \times 10^{11} L_{\odot}$. The mass of G1 (out to the A image) is of order $1 \times 10^{12} M_{\odot}$ hence for these models $M/L \geq 4$.

Model No.	Mass of G1 out to A ($10^{12} M_{\odot}$)	Central density of cluster ($10^{-23} \text{ Kg m}^{-3}$)
Model 1	1.03	1.63
Model 2	1.29	1.45
Model 5	0.99	1.57

Table 6.11: The mass of G1 out to image A and the central density of the cluster at $z \approx 0.355$.

6.15 Summary

We have presented several models involving double and single plane solutions which accurately reproduce the main features of the double quasar, 0957+561. In all models the third image is predicted to lie ≈ 110 mas due south of the main lensing galaxy G1 and is notably fainter than the other images ($B2/B1 < 0.8\%$). If the four galaxies at $z \approx 0.503$ are just a small group, then their effect on the imaging process is probably insignificant. If on the other hand they are the brightest members of a cluster of galaxies (similar to the cluster at $z \approx 0.355$) then the effect of this cluster cannot be ignored. However, if model 5 proves to be typical of double plane models then the mass distribution in the first plane does not appear to be significantly different from single plane solutions. According to models 1,2 and 5 a mass of $\approx 10^{12} M_{\odot}$ seems to be a reasonable estimate of the mass of G1 out to the A image. The total mass is highly model dependent but is likely to be several times greater. With a $M/L \sim 340$ most of the mass in the cluster at $z \approx 0.355$ must be in the form of dark matter.

Chapter 7

Conclusions and suggestions for further work

The rule on staying alive as a forecaster is to give 'em a number or give 'em a date but never give 'em both at once — Jane Bryant Quinn.

7.1 Overview

At the outset of this project the main aim was to investigate the mass distribution of the main lensing galaxy, G1, which is partly responsible for the multiple images seen in the double quasar, 0957+561 A,B. To that end two observational programs have been completed to give more constraints on lens models of this system. These observations have comprised of high resolution radio maps of the A and B images and a spectroscopic survey of the brightest galaxies in the field surrounding 0957+561. To take advantage of these these new data two major computer programs were developed and used to produce a number of different lens models including a 'double lens model' which could reproduce the main features of 0957+561. In this the final chapter we present an overview of the main results of chapters 4, 5 and 6 while casting an eye forward to future observations of the double quasar and gravitational lenses in general.

7.2 VLBI results

The VLBI radio observations were presented in chapter 4. The hybrid maps and model plots produced for both images leave little doubt that they are the result of multiple imaging of a single background source. Accurate values for the core-jet separations in both images have been determined and differences in the form of the jet confirm the result first obtained by GOR88, that the A and B images have opposite parity. The increase in the magnification ratio from 0.63 in the jet to 0.79 in the core is attributed to micro-lensing rather than brightness changes in the core. A wide field map of the B image has detected the compact component G' first discovered by Gorenstein *et al.* (1983). Comparison between this map and the MERLIN $\lambda 18$ cm map show that there

is a real positional offset between G' and G which is best explained by asymmetrical structure in G .

7.3 Spectroscopic results

The optical spectroscopy of the lensing cluster (chapter 5) at $z \approx 0.355$ has allowed us to determine a luminosity-weighted centre for the cluster which places it much closer to $G1$ and the images than the position originally suggested by YGKOW. Cross correlation of the spectra has allowed us to estimate the velocity dispersion, $\sigma_v \approx 548 \text{ km s}^{-1}$.

Perhaps the single most important result to emerge from this thesis was the discovery of four galaxies lying close to each other on the sky and with the same redshift, $z \approx 0.503$. It still remains unclear whether the four galaxies are the brightest members of cluster similar to that at $z \approx 0.355$ or just an isolated group of galaxies. It is somewhat ironic that the very observations that appeared most likely to narrow the range of possible lens models have had exactly the opposite effect.

7.4 Lens modelling results

Several lens models (double and single plane cases) have been presented in chapter 6. One important point which had not been clear to the author before embarking on this project was the importance of testing lens models both in the image plane and in the source plane and this was highlighted by the discovery of 'extra' images in an otherwise good lens model produced by Higgs (1984). The single plane lens models presented in chapter 6 show the velocity dispersion of the cluster at $z \approx 0.355$ to be significantly smaller than previous lens models. Even so the velocity dispersion in these models is still higher than the measured value (see above). However, if the cluster is appreciably flattened (as suggested by YGKOW's original observations) then this can help explain this anomalous result. The models (double and single) show the mass of $G1$ (out to the A image) to be $\approx 10^{12} M_{\odot}$. Most of the cluster mass must be in the form of dark matter with $M/L \sim 340$.

An investigation into the effect of the second cluster at $z \approx 0.503$ on the imaging suggests that if the size and extent of the cluster is similar to that found at $z \approx 0.355$ it may play an important role in the imaging. If this is the case then it is difficult to see how an accurate lens mass distribution for cosmological studies can be obtained. Nevertheless, we may be able to acquire valuable information about double lens systems

and large separation lenses in general. If we are to establish the magnitude of this effect one way or the other then further observations and modelling will be required. The modelling efforts described here are in no way complete and it is clear that the 'brute force' search method used by BILDEN is unsatisfactory for this type of work. The inclusion of a minimisation procedure (though perhaps not at the start of the search procedure), would reduce the time required to produce an optimum solution.

7.5 How big is big ?

There can be little doubt that in the coming years we will be able to measure the structural length, ellipticity and position angle of the main lensing galaxy G1 with much improved accuracy. However, if the range of lens models is to be narrowed still further then more our first concern must be to determine better the extent and size of the second 'cluster' at $z \approx 0.503$. Further multi-slit spectroscopy is unlikely to be rewarding since the galaxies are likely to be fainter than $r = 21$. It may be that the faint object spectrograph on the William Herschel Telescope (WHT) may be able to do significantly better as the throughput of the system and the seeing is believed to be superior. Smoker (1990) has used the technique of multi-colour, intermediate-band photometry (Ellis *et al.* 1985) on the field surrounding 0957+561 but the results are inconclusive. Certainly galaxies R4, R7, R23 and R33 are at $z \approx 0.50$ but Smoker (private communication) is not confident of being able to classify galaxies any fainter than this.

There is some evidence (Smoker 1990) that the cluster at $z \approx 0.355$ extends far beyond the CCD image taken by YGKOW. If this is true then the cluster centre presented in chapter 5 may still be in error. One way of re-determining the cluster centre is suggested by some recent work conducted by Tyson, Valdes & Wenk (1990). They have obtained very deep multi-colour CCD images of the clusters Abell 1689 and CL 1409+52. These reveal a population of faint blue galaxies which appear to be tangentially distorted (small scale versions of the giant luminous arcs caused by comparatively rare caustic alignments) by the lensing action of the foreground cluster. What makes this discovery potentially useful is that the the galaxies are stretched along a circle centered on the centre of mass of the lens. There is no reason why this same technique could not be applied to 0957+561. Indeed an 'I' filter image taken by Smoker (1990) shows two galaxies which appear very elongated (extent $\approx 10''$) both lying $\approx$

150" from the B image and both concave towards the general direction of the cluster centre. Using this method the cluster centre may be determined accurately with only a modest amount of effort and telescope time.

7.6 The elusive third image

The discovery of the faint third image is perhaps the last remaining piece of the jigsaw that would make the story of 0957+561 complete. Needless to say 0957+561 will be one of the first objects to be observed with the Hubble Space Telescope (HST) in the hope of doing just this. At the time of writing the HST has been delivered safely into orbit but the process of instrument verification has only just begun. In the meantime there is still a possibility that the third image may reveal itself in high resolution radio maps of the B image. Building on the success of the wide-field hybrid maps presented in this thesis, observations have been made using a global VLBI array (5 EVN and 4 USVN telescopes) for which the author is principle investigator. These data have been correlated but no maps have yet been made. We have computed the visibilities we can expect using a plausible GOR88 - type model for the B image and a scaled-down model for the third image.¹ Realistic values of thermal noise were added to the simulated data. The data were then Fourier inverted and CLEANed. The resulting simulated map of the third image is shown in figure 7.1. We can be confident that if a core-jet like structure is associated with G' on the scale suggested by Rogers (1989) then these observations with a r.m.s. noise of $\approx 35 \mu\text{Jy}$ will be able to detect it.

A similar program is anticipated for the new enhanced MERLIN array at $\lambda 6$ cm. With the addition of the new 32 m telescope at Cambridge, MERLIN will have an angular resolution of 50 mas and r.m.s. noise (after a full 12 hour imaging track) of $\approx 50 \mu\text{Jy}$. These observations may also be sensitive to the brighter parts of the bridge of emission which is seen between the B and G components. However, at $\lambda 6$ cm this emission is very weak and the fierceness of the beam may mean that nearly all of the extended emission will be resolved out. At $\lambda 18$ cm the situation is much more promising since the emission is stronger here than at $\lambda 6$ cm. With a resolution of (≈ 150 mas) approximately 6 beams can be placed across the bridge of emission. One can do even better if the source is simultaneously observed with the large Effelsberg and Westerbork antennas. Combining the short spacing MERLIN data with the larger

¹The flux and core-jet separation of the third image is based on the the suggestion by Rogers (1989) (see section 3.7) that G' may be the third image.

Figure 7.1: Simulated map of the third image.

spacing VLBI data should allow the bridge to be mapped (≈ 13 beams in extent) in greater detail than ever before.

Even if all of the above programs fail to discover the third image we can expect useful upper limits to be placed on its flux density.

7.7 Theoretical developments

If the second cluster at $z \approx 0.503$ really does play a major role in the imaging of the double quasar then it is certainly worth while investing some time and effort in the study of multiple plane systems. Already double lens models have been suggested for other lenses including 2016+112 where it is difficult to account for all the observations in detail. An attempt to classify double lens systems by their caustic structure has been made by Kochanek & Apostolakis (1988) but they only consider the effects of galactic size masses. It would not be difficult to modify LENCAL so that caustics could be plotted for any particular lens model under investigation. The results of such an exercise for double lens models might prove very interesting.

7.8 Lensing in general

Some recent work by Hinshaw & Krauss (1987) suggests that the peak in the image separation distribution for lensed systems is at $\sim 2''$ which agrees well with the observed image separations. Beyond a separation of $2''$ the distribution is expected to fall off quite sharply and to date there is only one probable lens candidate (1413+117) for which the separation is of order $1''$. One factor that may severely affect this work is the strong selection bias against finding close separation lenses ($< 1''$). However, this will be removed shortly by a new generation of high resolution instruments including MERLIN and the VLBA (Very Long Baseline Array). The HST is unlikely to play a major role in lens surveys but it will prove extremely useful for finding faint lensing galaxies and structure in the images. In this way MERLIN, the HST and the VLBA will nicely complement each other.

If the point at which the distribution 'turns over' can be accurately determined then in principle this information can be used to provide important clues to the distribution of matter in the universe. However, the statistical models are based on simple assumptions about the lens and source population. In particular the effect of a non-zero source size must be incorporated into these models so that the new class of Einstein ring lensed systems can be included in the distribution.

7.9 Individual lens systems

Although lensing statistics will begin to play a more dominant role in the subject as a whole, particular cases will nevertheless be essential for determining the mass distribution of individual lensing galaxies. It is instructive to ask ourselves what kind of lensed system would we like to discover if we could pick and choose.

First of all let us consider the lens mass distribution. Clearly we do not want a complicated system in which more than one lens is present. This restricts us to a single galactic type lens for which the image separation will be $\sim 2''$. However, in this case nature conspires against us, since for small separation lenses the images lie close to the denser regions of the lens mass and therefore run the risk of being micro-lensed. This means that the important constraints of image amplification ratio (R) and the time delay are no longer available or at best fairly inaccurate. If the lensed source happens to be radio loud and the images have common extended features then the effects of micro-lensing are reduced and R may be accurately determined. In addition, providing

the radio core is variable then frequent radio monitoring should eventually produce a value for the time delay.

Figure 7.2: Simulated map of the B image.

Secondly, it is important that the lens itself lies close to the observer. Then the ratio of lens–source and observer–source distance is less sensitive to the choice of cosmological model and the lens itself is close enough so that its internal structure can be studied in detail.

An additional reason for the source to be extended is that the (radio) images provide a two dimensional distribution of image brightness and can therefore furnish far more information about the shape and extent of the lensing potential than images of unresolved point sources possibly can. It is possible that the high resolution images of 0957+561 that we expect to obtain from the new VLBI observations (see section 7.6) may be sensitive enough for the technique of Digital Source Reconstruction (DiSoR)

(which has been applied so successfully in the case of MG1131+0456) to be applied to the A and B core-jet images. A simulated map of the B image is shown in figure 7.2.

7.10 The role of 0957+561

It will be noted that 0957+561 is not the 'ideal' lens described above, mainly because the effect of the lensing galaxy G1 is difficult to separate from the surrounding cluster. However, it is this added complexity that continues to make this system worthy of further study. It seems likely that in the coming years this intriguing source, the double quasar, will surprise and delight us yet again.

Appendix A

Observed visibilities and model plots

We present plots of the amplitudes and closure phases for both the A and the B image EVN data sets as discussed in chapter 4. The integration time is 780 seconds. The solid lines represent the visibility predicted by the models produced by the MODELFIT program.

Figure A.1: Plots of the amplitude visibilities for image A. The amplitudes predicted by the 2 component gaussian models (see table 4.2) are shown by the solid line.

Figure A.2: The plots show the closure phases for image A. The closure phases predicted by the 2 component gaussian models (see table 4.3) are shown by the solid line.

Figure A.3: Plots of the amplitude visibilities for image B. The amplitudes predicted by the 2 component gaussian models (see table 4.3) is shown by the solid line.

Figure A.4: Plots of the closure phase visibilities for image B. The closure phases predicted by the 2 component gaussian models (see table 4.3) is shown by the solid line.

Appendix B

Spectra of 24 objects in the field

We present optical spectra of objects in the field of 0957+561 A,B. They are arranged in order of decreasing brightness i.e. in order of rank number. The rank number is shown at the top of each plot. The flux scale is in arbitrary units and may not be comparable from one plot to the next.

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